

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3779–3902

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MSL MAHLI Technical Report 0035, version 1
04 April 2024

Citation: R. A. Yingst, M. E. Minitti, D. M. Fey, J. E. Huggett, N. G. Moore, C. Rodriguez Sanchez-Vahamonde (2024) Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3779–3902, version 1, *MSL MAHLI Technical Report 0035*. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10928130>

Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0035

Cover photo

MAHLI view of fin features called Terra Firme, located in the Mg Sulfate-Bearing unit of lower Aeolis Mons, acquired on Sol 3800. Illuminated by sunlight from the upper right, this is MAHLI image 3800MH0001900010804764C00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity's 3779th and 3902nd Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3779 and 3902.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 3779–3902*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 34 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 24 March 2023 through 29 July 2023.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3779 through 3902 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3779 – 3902						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Heading towards the Ubajara Drill Site	26 Mar 23	3780	12	73	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the targets Capanapro and Amanauo.
	27 Mar 23	3781	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3780 were merged.
Heading towards the Ubajara Drill Site	11 Apr 23	3796	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Tarilandia and the focus stack images were merged.
	13 Apr 23	3798	10	96	0	MAHLI acquired a 6x1 mosaic on the target Cantario and imaged the DRT-brushed target Cupixi.
	14 Apr 23	3799	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 3798 were merged.
	15 Apr 23	3800	15	80	0	MAHLI imaged the target Terra Firme and the DRT-brushed target Lorenzo. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	16 Apr 23	3801	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3800 were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3460 (data from Sols 3562–3724) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.
	18 Apr 23	3803	1	28	2	MAHLI imaged the ChemCam RWEB window and internal hardware. The focus stack images were also merged.
	22 Apr 23	3807	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Floresta and the target Calama.
	23 Apr 23	3808	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3807 were merged.
	25 Apr 23/ 26 Apr 23	3810	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Anortosito_Repartimento and the focus stack images were merged.
	27 Apr 23/ 28 Apr 23	3812	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Armero and the focus stack images were merged.
At the Ubajara Drill Site	03 May 23	3817	6	36	0	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Ubajara before and after an attempted drill bit preload test.
	03 May 23	3818	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 3817 were merged.
	05 May 23	3819	5	42	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Ubajara after DRT. The focus stack images were also merged.
	07 May 23	3821	8	56	5	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Ubajara after a drill bit preload test. MAHLI also imaged the targets Ilha_Grande and Bwesse_Kiiki. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	09 May 23	3823	2	4	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Ubajara sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Ubajara sample discard pile.
	20 May 23	3834	3	14	1	MAHLI imaged the Ubajara drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.
	21 May 23	3835	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the Ubajara drill hole cuttings.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3779 – 3902						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At the Ubajara Drill Site	23 May 23	3837	6	51	3	During the day, MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3461 through 4854 (data from Sols 3725-3801) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. MAHLI also imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the DRT-brushed target Apetina. The corresponding focus stack images for the day-time imaging were merged as well. At night, MAHLI re-imaged the DRT-brushed target Apetina using different combinations of the LEDs, including ultraviolet to seek fluorescence.
	24 May 23	3838	0	0	1	Focus stack images from the Sol 3837 night imaging of Apetina were merged.
	25 May 23	3839	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Zipaquira and the focus stack images were merged.
Heading towards the Jau crater cluster	31 May 23	3845	8	56	0	MAHLI acquired a 1x2 mosaic on the target Cumbal and then imaged the DRT-brushed target Cujubim.
Heading towards the Jau crater cluster	01 Jun 23	3846	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3845 were merged.
	07 Jun 23	3851	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Aporema and the focus stack images were merged.
	09 Jun 23	3853	5	47	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Massaco and Saul. The focus stack images were also merged.
	11 Jun 23	3855	4	5	0	At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	14 Jun 23	3858	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Terebito and the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Jun 23	3859	11	85	0	MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHLI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Rio Madeira and the target Macapa.
	16 Jun 23	3860	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3859 were merged.
	18 Jun 23	3862	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Surpresa.
	20 Jun 23	3864	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3862 were merged.
	22 Jun 23	3866	11	94	0	MAHLI imaged the target Feneos, which includes a 1x5 mosaic, and the DRT-brushed target Kastria Spring.
	23 Jun 23	3867	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 3866 were merged.
	27 Jun 23	3871	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Lousoi and the focus stack images were merged.
29 Jun 23	3873	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Madero and the target Vesini. The focus stack images were also merged.	
Heading towards the Jau crater cluster	03 Jul 23/ 04 Jul 23	3877	10	76	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Trapeza and the target Analipsi. The focus stack images, excluding the stereo-1 before DRT focus stack images of Trapeza, were also merged.
	04 Jul 23	3878	20	20	1	The focus stack images for Sol 3877 stereo-1 before DRT imaging of Trapeza were merged. MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
	06 Jul 23	3880	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Roghi and acquired a 3x1 mosaic on the target Xerocambos. The focus stack images were also merged.
	11 Jul 23	3885	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Planitero and the focus stack images were merged.
	13 Jul 23/ 14 Jul 23	3887	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Sounion and the focus stack images were merged.
	16 Jul 23	3889	10	60	0	MAHLI imaged the target Thermopylae and the DRT-brushed target Zachlorou.
	17 Jul 23	3890	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3889 were merged.
19 Jul 23	3892	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Nasia and the focus stack images were merged.	

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3779 – 3902						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Traversing through the Jau crater cluster	22 Jul 23	3895	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Rio_Javari and the DRT-brushed target La_Trinite.
	24 Jul 23	3897	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3895 were merged.
	25 Jul 23	3898	5	34	3	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the DRT-brushed target Mamore. The focus stack images were also merged.
	26 Jul 23	3899	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Guainia and Mocambo. The focus stack images were also merged.
	27 Jul 23	3900	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Porta_Walter and the target Purace.
	28 Jul 23	3901	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3900 were merged.
	29 Jul 23	3902	4	32	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Jamari.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 0001580010101

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 0001580010101

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 0001580010101

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 0001580010101

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → C00

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → C00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3779–3902 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3780, 3796, 3798, 3800, 3803, 3807, 3810, 3812, 3817, 3819, 3821, 3823, 3834, 3835, 3837, 3839, 3845, 3851, 3853, 3855, 3858, 3859, 3862, 3866, 3871, 3873, 3877, 3878, 3880, 3885, 3887, 3889, 3892, 3895, 3898, 3899, 3900, 3902.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

SOL 3780 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI calibration target														
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.														
mhl100371	BAR TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	3780MH0003710011304527C00	4527	14373	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100372	CENT TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	3780MH0003720011304529C00	4529	14367	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE - 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE													
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET													
	3780MH0003740011304531C00	4531	12962	30.3	28.4	-2.3	2.6	113.6	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6	
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS													
	3780MH0003740021304532C00	4532	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	3780MH0003730011304534C00	4534	13946	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named Capanapro													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	3780MH0001900011304536C00	4536	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3780MH0002990011304538C00	4538	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304609R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304610S00					
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3780MH0002990011304548C00	4548	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304607R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304608S00					
mhl100174	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm										
	3780MH0001740011304558C00	4558	14604	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304605R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304606S00					

target named Amanauo													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	3780MH0001900011304568C00	4568	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3780MH0002990011304570C00	4570	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304603R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304604S00					
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3780MH0002990011304580C00	4580	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304601R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304602S00					
mhl100796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	3780MH0007960011304590C00	4590	15136	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304599R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3781MH0001630001304600S00					

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3796 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Tarilandia – after DRT													
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3796MH0001900011304612C00	4612	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3796MH0001820011304614C00	4614	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304647R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304648S00								
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3796MH0001820011304624C00	4624	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304645R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304646S00								
mhl00184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm											
	3796MH0001840011304634C00	4634	14762	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304643R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3796MH0001930001304644S00								

SOL 3798 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Cantario - a 6 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
mhl100299	POSITION 1 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011304650C00	4650	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.0	0.6	1608 1198	5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904761R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904762S00		
mhl100299	POSITION 2 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011304660C00	4660	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2 0.2	30.7	0.5	1608 1198	4.9 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904759R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904760S00		
mhl100299	POSITION 3 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011204670C00	4670	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2 0.1	30.5	0.5	1608 1198	4.9 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904757R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904758S00		
mhl100299	POSITION 4 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011204680C00	4680	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2 0.1	30.4	0.5	1608 1198	4.9 3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904755R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904756S00		
mhl100299	POSITION 5 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011204690C00	4690	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2 0.2	30.8	0.6	1608 1198	5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904753R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904754S00		
mhl100299	POSITION 6 OF 6									
	3798MH0002990011104700C00	4700	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2 0.2	31.0	0.6	1608 1198	5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904751R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904752S00		

target named Cupixi - after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW									
	3798MH0007060011104710C00	4710	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8 2.0	100.5	6.7	1608 1198	16.2 12.0
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1									
	3798MH0007230011104713C00	4713	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.3	0.6	1608 1198	5.0 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904749R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904750S00		
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2									
	3798MH0007230011104724C00	4724	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.3	0.6	1608 1198	5.0 3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904747R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904748S00		
mhl100794	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW									
	3798MH0007940011104735C00	4735	14828	3.4	1.5	-0.1 0.1	19.0	0.2	1608 1198	3.1 2.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904745R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904746S00		

SOL 3800 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

*NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		

target named Terra_Firme

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3800MH0001900010804764C00	4764	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
mhl100459	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3800MH0004590010804766C00	4766	14222	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000604853R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000604854S00	
mhl100459	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3800MH0004590010804776C00	4776	14184	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000604851R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000604852S00	

target named Lorencio – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3800MH0007060010804786C00	4786	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100763	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007630010804789C00	4789	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000704849R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000604850S00	
mhl100763	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007630010804800C00	4800	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000704847R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000704848S00	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007050010804811C00	4811	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007050010804813C00	4813	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007050010804815C00	4815	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
mhl100794	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	3800MH0007940010804817C00	4817	15063	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000704845R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000704846S00	
mhl100763	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1	3800MH0007630010804828C00	4828	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3801MH0001630000704843R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3801MH0001630000704844S00	

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	MANUAL FOCUS	3800MH0003120000704838C00	4838	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm											
	MANUAL FOCUS	3800MH0003120010704839C00	4839	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	MANUAL FOCUS	3800MH0003260000704840C00	4840	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	MANUAL FOCUS	3800MH0003260000704841C00	4841	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl100228	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm											
	3800MH0002280000704842C00	4842	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3803 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

ChemCam mirror/window and RWEB

ChemCam mirror/window and RWEB														
SEQUENCE	RWEB FULL FRAME		MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	STANDOFF (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)												
mhl100520	3803MH000520001140002C00		2	13100	22.2	20.3	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	1608	1198	13.7	10.2
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3803MH0007680001400031R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3803MH0007680001400032S00								
	MANUAL FOCUS ON INTERIOR HARDWARE													
	3803MH0005200041400020C00		20	12990	28.3	26.4	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	1024	1200	10.9	12.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3803MH0007680001400029R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3803MH0007680001400030S00									

SOL 3807 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Floresta – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3807MH0001900011400034C00	34	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3807MH0001820011400036C00	36	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3808MH0002270001400095R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3808MH0002270001400096S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3807MH0001820011400046C00	46	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3808MH0002270001400093R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3808MH0002270001400094S00	
mhl100337	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	3807MH0003370011400056C00	56	14650	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3808MH0002270001400091R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3808MH0002270001400092S00	

target named Calama

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3807MH0001900011400066C00	66	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3807MH0002990011400068C00	68	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3808MH0002270001400089R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3808MH0002270001400090S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3807MH0002990011400078C00	78	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3808MH0002270001400087R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3808MH0002270001400088S00	

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3810 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Anortosito_Repartimento - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	3810MH0001900011400098C00	98	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3810MH0001680011400100C00	100	14055	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3810MH0001930001400133R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3810MH0001930001400134S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3810MH0001680011400110C00	110	14059	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3810MH0001930001400131R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3810MH0001930001400132S00
mhl100796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm												
	3810MH0007960011400120C00	120	15290	2.5	0.6	0.0	0.0	15.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.5	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3810MH0001930001400129R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3810MH0001930001400130S00

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3812 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Armero – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3812MH0001900011400136C00	136	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3812MH0001730011400138C00	138	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3812MH0001930001400171R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3812MH0001930001400172S00
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3812MH0001730011400148C00	148	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3812MH0001930001400169R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3812MH0001930001400170S00
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	3812MH0003020011400158C00	158	14713	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3812MH0001930001400167R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3812MH0001930001400168S00

SOL 3817 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named **Ubajara** – before DRT

mhl100197	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3817MH0001970011400174C00	174	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100197	CONTEXT STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3817MH0001970011400176C00	176	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3817MH0001730011400178C00	178	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3818MH0001930001400213R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3818MH0001930001400214S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3817MH0001730011400188C00	188	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3818MH0001930001400211R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3818MH0001930001400212S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3817MH0001730011400198C00	198	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3818MH0001930001400209R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3818MH0001930001400210S00	

intended drill target named **Ubajara** – before DRT – after attempted drill bit pre-load test

mhl100465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	3817MH0004650011400208C00	208	12897	36.3	34.4	-3.2	3.9	134.5	12.5	1608	1198	21.6	16.1

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3819 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Ubajara – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3819MH0001900011400216C00	216	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3819MH0001820011400218C00	218	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3819MH0001530001400263R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3819MH0001530001400264S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3819MH0001820011400228C00	228	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3819MH0001530001400261R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3819MH0001530001400262S00	
mhl00426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3819MH0004260011400238C00	238	15125	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3819MH0001530001400259R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3819MH0001530001400260S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3819MH0001820011400248C00	248	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3819MH0001530001400257R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3819MH0001530001400258S00	

SOL 3821 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named **Ubajara** – after sol 3819 DRT – after drill bit pre-load test

mhl100465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	3821MH0004650011400266C00	266	12896	36.4	34.5	-3.2	3.9	134.9	12.6	1608	1198	21.7	16.2

target named **Itha_Grande**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3821MH0001900011400268C00	268	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3821MH0001520011400270C00	270	14105	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400329R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3821MH0002270001400330S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3821MH0001520011400280C00	280	14106	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400327R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3821MH0002270001400328S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3821MH0001520011400290C00	290	14098	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400325R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3821MH0002270001400326S00	

target named **Bwesse_Kiiki**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3821MH0001900011400300C00	300	13045	24.9	23.0	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.9	1608	1198	15.2	11.3		
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3821MH0002990011400302C00	302	14308	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400323R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3821MH0002270001400324S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3821MH0002990011400312C00	312	14303	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400321R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3821MH0002270001400322S00	

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3823 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended sample discard site for planned Ubajara drill sample

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm									
	3823MH0001900011400332C00	332	13038	25.3	23.4	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5
mhl00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	3823MH0001220011400334C00	334	14250	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1

UPDATED: 25_October_2023

SOL 3834 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Ubajara drill hole

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100197	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3834MH0001970011400336C00	336	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm											
	3834MH0007740011400338C00	338	13560	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.5

Ubajara drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3834MH0001520011400340C00	340	14067	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3834MH0002580001400349R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3834MH0002580001400350S00					

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3835 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Ubajara drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhli00122	3835MH0001220011400352C00	352	14063	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3837 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	3837MH0000950011400354C00	354	13259	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

target named Apetina - after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 25 cm										
	3837MH0001900011400356C00	356	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 5 cm										
	3837MH0001820011400358C00	358	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400391R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400392S00					
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 5 cm										
	3837MH0001820011400368C00	368	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400389R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400390S00					
mhl100184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 2 cm										
	3837MH0001840011400378C00	378	14660	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400387R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400388S00					

target named Apetina - after DRT - night imaging

NOTE: DETERMINATION OF RANGE AND SCALE FROM MOTOR COUNT CAN SOMETIMES BE LESS ACCURATE VIA NIGHT IMAGING RELATIVE TO DAYTIME IMAGING.

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100861	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~ 5 cm										
	AFTER A 480x480 AUTOFOCUS SUB-FRAME, THERE ARE MULTIPLE FULL-FRAME IMAGES WITH DIFFERENT LED COMBINATIONS; THE IMAGE LISTED HERE IS THE ONE WITH GROUP 2 LEDS ON												
3837MH00009610031400395C00	395	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3838MH0002580001400410R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3838MH0002580001400411S00					

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3839 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Zipaquira – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3839MH0001900011400413C00	413	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3839MH0001680011400415C00	415	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3839MH0001930001400448R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3839MH0001930001400449S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3839MH0001680011400425C00	425	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3839MH0001930001400446R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3839MH0001930001400447S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3839MH0007430011400435C00	435	15108	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3839MH0001930001400444R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3839MH0001930001400445S00

SOL 3845 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Cumbal** – a 1 x 2 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100172	POSITION 1 OF 2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm									
	3845MH0001720011400451C00	451	13150	20.2	18.3	-1.1	1.1	78.0	3.8	1608	1198	12.5	9.3
mhl100172	POSITION 2 OF 2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 20 cm									
	3845MH0001720011400453C00	453	13151	20.1	18.2	-1.1	1.1	77.8	3.8	1608	1198	12.5	9.3

target named **Cujubim** – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	3845MH0001900011400455C00	455	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 3													
	3845MH0001820011400457C00	457	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400514R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3846MH0002270001400515S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 3													
	3845MH0001820011400467C00	467	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400512R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3846MH0002270001400513S00	
mhl100184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 3													
	3845MH0001840011400477C00	477	14693	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400510R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3846MH0002270001400511S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1													
	3845MH0001820011400487C00	487	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400508R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3846MH0002270001400509S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2													
	3845MH0001820011400497C00	497	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400506R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3846MH0002270001400507S00	

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3851 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Aporema – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3851MH0001900011400517C00	517	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3851MH0001680011400519C00	519	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3851MH0001930001400552R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3851MH0001930001400553S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3851MH0001680011400529C00	529	14033	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3851MH0001930001400550R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3851MH0001930001400551S00
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3851MH0008480011400539C00	539	15200	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3851MH0001930001400548R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3851MH0001930001400549S00

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3853 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Massaco**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100862	CONTEXT STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	3853MH0008620011400555C00	555	13050	24.6	22.7	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	1608	1198	15.1	11.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400607R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400608S00					
mhl100862	CONTEXT STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	3853MH0008620011400566C00	566	13048	24.8	22.9	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400605R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400606S00					

target named **Saul**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	3853MH0007060011400577C00	577	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	3853MH0007230011400580C00	580	14226	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400603R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400604S00					
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	3853MH0007230011400591C00	591	14166	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400601R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3853MH0008170001400602S00					

UPDATED: 19_June_2023

SOL 3855 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhli00312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	3855MH0003120001400609C00	609	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhli00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm											
	3855MH0003120011400610C00	610	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhli00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	3855MH0003260001400611C00	611	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhli00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
	3855MH0003260001400612C00	612	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhli00228	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm											
	3855MH0002280001400613C00	613	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 15_June_2023

SOL 3858 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Terebito - after DRT															
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	3858MH0001680011400615C00	615	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3858MH0001930001400650R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3858MH0001930001400651S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	3858MH0001680011400625C00	625	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3858MH0001930001400648R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3858MH0001930001400649S00	
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm												
	3858MH0007430011400635C00	635	15144	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3858MH0001930001400646R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								3858MH0001930001400647S00	
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	3858MH0001900011400645C00	645	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		

SOL 3859 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

MAHLI sky flat field images – dust cover closed – first set

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS – ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120001400652C00	652	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120011400653C00	653	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120021400654C00	654	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
3859MH0007120031400655C00	655	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0007120041400656C00	656	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images – dust cover open – first set

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS – ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530001400657C00	657	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530011400658C00	658	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530021400659C00	659	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
3859MH0004530031400660C00	660	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT – ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0004530041400661C00	661	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0004530051400662C00	662	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images – dust cover open – second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl100453	CLOSE FOCUS – ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530001400663C00	663	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530011400664C00	664	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0004530021400665C00	665	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
3859MH0004530031400666C00	666	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
PRE-LAUNCH FLAT FIELD EQUIVALENT – ~63.3 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0004530041400667C00	667	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0004530051400668C00	668	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images – dust cover closed – second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl100712	CLOSE FOCUS – ~2.04 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120001400669C00	669	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~3.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120011400670C00	670	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
	3859MH0007120021400671C00	671	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm STANDOFF EQUIVALENT – ~26.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE FOCUS POSITION – MANUAL FOCUS												
3859MH0007120031400672C00	672	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
INFINITY FOCUS – MANUAL FOCUS													
3859MH0007120041400673C00	673	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

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target named Rio_Madeira - after DRT															
mhli00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	3859MH0001900011400675C00	675	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3859MH0001820011400677C00	677	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400747R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400748S00	
mhli00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3859MH0001820011400687C00	687	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400745R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400746S00	
mhli00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm													
	3859MH0007430011400697C00	697	15086	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400743R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400744S00	

target named Macapa															
mhli00678	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	3859MH0006780011400707C00	707	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400741R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400742S00	
mhli00306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3859MH0003060011400718C00	718	13958	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400739R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400740S00	
mhli00306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3859MH0003060011400728C00	728	13976	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400737R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3860MH0001630001400738S00	

SOL 3862 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Surpresa</i> – before DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3862MH0001900011400750C00	750	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3862MH0001820011400752C00	752	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400823R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400824S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3862MH0001820011400762C00	762	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400821R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400822S00	

target named <i>Surpresa</i> – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3862MH0001900011400772C00	772	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3862MH0001820011400774C00	774	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400819R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400820S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3862MH0001820011400784C00	784	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400817R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400818S00	
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3862MH0007430011400794C00	794	15073	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400815R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400816S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3862MH0001820011400804C00	804	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3864MH0001630001400813R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3864MH0001630001400814S00	

SOL 3866 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		

target named **Feneos** – a 1 x 5 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
mhli00190	3866MH0001900011400826C00	826	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7 / 1.9	98.4	6.4	1608 / 1198	15.8 / 11.8
POSITION 1 OF 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00299	3866MH0002990011400828C00	828	14246	5.5	3.6	-0.1 / 0.1	26.1	0.4	1608 / 1198	4.2 / 3.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400933R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400936S00										
POSITION 2 OF 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00299	3866MH0002990011400838C00	838	14217	5.6	3.7	-0.1 / 0.1	26.6	0.4	1608 / 1198	4.3 / 3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400931R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400934S00										
POSITION 3 OF 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00299	3866MH0002990011400848C00	848	14105	6.2	4.3	-0.1 / 0.1	28.7	0.5	1608 / 1198	4.6 / 3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400931R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400932S00										
POSITION 4 OF 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00299	3866MH0002990011400858C00	858	14115	6.1	4.2	-0.1 / 0.1	28.5	0.5	1608 / 1198	4.6 / 3.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400929R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400930S00										
POSITION 5 OF 5 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00299	3866MH0002990011400868C00	868	14052	6.5	4.6	-0.2 / 0.1	29.8	0.5	1608 / 1198	4.8 / 3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400927R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400928S00										

target named **Kastria_Spring** – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
mhli00190	3866MH0001900011400878C00	878	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8 / 2.0	100.9	6.7	1608 / 1198	16.2 / 12.1
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00182	APXS RASTER SPOT 1 3866MH0001820011400880C00	880	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2 / 0.2	31.5	0.6	1608 / 1198	5.1 / 3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400925R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400926S00										
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00182	APXS RASTER SPOT 1 3866MH0001820011400890C00	890	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2 / 0.2	31.9	0.6	1608 / 1198	5.1 / 3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400923R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400924S00										
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm										
mhli00302	APXS RASTER SPOT 1 3866MH0003020011400900C00	900	14640	4.0	2.1	-0.1 / 0.1	20.8	0.3	1608 / 1198	3.4 / 2.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400921R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400922S00										
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
mhli00182	APXS RASTER SPOT 2 3866MH0001820011400910C00	910	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2 / 0.2	31.3	0.6	1608 / 1198	5.0 / 3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS: BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400919R00 RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3867MH0005360001400920S00										

UPDATED: 28_June_2023

SOL 3871 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lousoi – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3871MH0001900011400938C00	938	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3871MH0001820011400940C00	940	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3871MH0001930001400973R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3871MH0001930001400974S00
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3871MH0001820011400950C00	950	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3871MH0001930001400971R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3871MH0001930001400972S00
mhl00176	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	3871MH0001760011400960C00	960	14638	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3871MH0001930001400969R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3871MH0001930001400970S00

SOL 3873 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Madero** – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3873MH0001900011400976C00	976	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3873MH0001680011400978C00	978	14070	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3873MH0002270001401037R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3873MH0002270001401038S00	
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3873MH0001680011400988C00	988	14053	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3873MH0002270001401035R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3873MH0002270001401036S00	
mhlI00184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	3873MH0001840011400998C00	998	14808	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3873MH0002270001401033R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3873MH0002270001401034S00	

target named **Vesini**

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3873MH0001900011401008C00	1008	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhlI00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3873MH0001520011401010C00	1010	14069	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3873MH0002270001401031R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3873MH0002270001401032S00	
mhlI00152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3873MH0001520011401020C00	1020	14074	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3873MH0002270001401029R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3873MH0002270001401030S00	

SOL 3877 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Trapeza – before DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3877MH0001900011401040C00	1040	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001680011401042C00	1042	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401127R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401126S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001680011401052C00	1052	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401125R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401126S00	

target named Trapeza – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3877MH0001900011401062C00	1062	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001680011401064C00	1064	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401123R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401124S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001680011401074C00	1074	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401121R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401122S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm											
	3877MH0003020011401084C00	1084	14688	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401119R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401120S00	

target named Analipsi															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3877MH0001900011401094C00	1094	13049	24.7	22.8	-1.5	1.7	93.8	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.2		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001820011401096C00	1096	14367	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401117R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401118S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3877MH0001820011401106C00	1106	14361	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401115R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3877MH0001710001401116S00	

SOL 3878 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 3878)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	3878MH0007690011401129E01	1129	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	3878MH0007700011401130E01	1130	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	3878MH0007710011401131E01	1131	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	3878MH0007720011401132E01	1132	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 3878)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	3878MH0007690011401133E01	1133	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	3878MH0007700011401134E01	1134	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	3878MH0007710011401135E01	1135	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	3878MH0007720011401136E01	1136	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 3878)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	3878MH0007690011401137E01	1137	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	3878MH0007700011401138E01	1138	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	3878MH0007710011401139E01	1139	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	3878MH0007720011401140E01	1140	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 3878)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	3878MH0007690011401141E01	1141	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	3878MH0007700011401142E01	1142	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	3878MH0007710011401143E01	1143	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	3878MH0007720011401144E01	1144	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE..

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 3878)													
mhl00769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	3878MH0007690011401145E01	1145	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~-612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	3878MH0007700011401146E01	1146	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~-408	~-137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	3878MH0007710011401147E01	1147	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~-489	~-210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	3878MH0007720011401148E01	1148	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~-450	~-175	1608	1198	~72	~54

SOL 3880 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Roghi - after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm											
	3880MH001900011401150C00	1150	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	3880MH001820011401152C00	1152	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401221R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401222500
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm											
	3880MH001820011401162C00	1162	14050	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401219R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401220500
mhl100184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm											
	3880MH001840011401172C00	1172	14790	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401217R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401218500

target named Xerocambos - a 3 x 1 mosaic

mhl100854	POSITION 1 OF 3		INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm												
	3880MH0008540011401182C00	1182	13103	22.1	20.2	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	1608	1198	13.6	10.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401215R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401216500	
mhl100854	POSITION 2 OF 3		INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm												
	3880MH0008540011401192C00	1192	13112	21.7	19.8	-1.2	1.3	83.3	4.4	1608	1198	13.4	10.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401213R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401214500	
mhl100854	POSITION 3 OF 3		INTENDED STANDOFF - 20 cm												
	3880MH0008540011401202C00	1202	13106	22.0	20.1	-1.2	1.3	84.2	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3880MH001630001401211R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3880MH001630001401212500	

UPDATED: 12_July_2023

SOL 3885 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Planitero														
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	3885MH0001900011401224C00	1224	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3885MH0001680011401226C00	1226	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3885MH0002650001401247R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3885MH0002650001401248S00
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3885MH0001680011401236C00	1236	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3885MH0002650001401245R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3885MH0002650001401246S00

UPDATED: 14_July_2023

SOL 3887 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Sounion - after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	3887MH0001900011401250C00	1250	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3887MH0001680011401252C00	1252	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3887MH0001930001401285R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3887MH0001930001401286S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3887MH0001680011401262C00	1262	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3887MH0001930001401283R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3887MH0001930001401284S00
mhl100796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm												
	3887MH0007960011401272C00	1272	14946	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3887MH0001930001401281R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3887MH0001930001401282S00

SOL 3889 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)			
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)		
target named Thermopylae															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3889MH0001900011401288C00	1288	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0001820011401290C00	1290	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3890MH0002270001401355R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3890MH0002270001401356S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0001820011401300C00	1300	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3890MH0002270001401353R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3890MH0002270001401354S00	
target named Zachlorou – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3889MH0001900011401310C00	1310	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100182	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0001820011401312C00	1312	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3890MH0002270001401351R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3890MH0002270001401352S00	
mhl100182	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0001820011401322C00	1322	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3890MH0002270001401349R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3890MH0002270001401350S00	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0007050011401332C00	1332	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0007050011401334C00	1334	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3889MH0007050011401336C00	1336	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl100426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3889MH0004260011401338C00	1338	15111	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3890MH0002270001401347R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3890MH0002270001401348S00	

UPDATED: 19_July_2023

SOL 3892 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Nasia</i>															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	3892MH0001900011401358C00	1358	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	3892MH0001730011401360C00	1360	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3892MH0001930001401393R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3892MH0001930001401394S00
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	3892MH0001730011401370C00	1370	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3892MH0001930001401391R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3892MH0001930001401392S00
mhl100796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 1 cm												
	3892MH0007960011401380C00	1380	15072	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3892MH0001930001401389R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3892MH0001930001401390S00

SOL 3895 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Rio_Javari**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3895MH0001900011401396C00	1396	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3895MH0001680011401398C00	1398	14223	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3897MH0002270001401457R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3897MH0002270001401458S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3895MH0001680011401408C00	1408	14224	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3897MH0002270001401455R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3897MH0002270001401456S00	

target named **La_Trinite - after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3895MH0001900011401418C00	1418	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3895MH0001680011401420C00	1420	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3897MH0002270001401453R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3897MH0002270001401454S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3895MH0001680011401430C00	1430	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3897MH0002270001401451R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3897MH0002270001401452S00	
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	3895MH0007430011401440C00	1440	15198	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3897MH0002270001401449R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3897MH0002270001401450S00	

UPDATED: 26_July_2023

SOL 3898 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	3898MH000950011401460C00	1460	13261	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.6	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.9

target named Mamore - after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	3898MH0001900011401462C00	1462	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3898MH0001820011401464C00	1464	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401497R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401498S00			
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	3898MH0001820011401474C00	1474	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401495R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401496S00			
mhl100184	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm										
	3898MH0001840011401484C00	1484	14736	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
		CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401493R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3898MH0001930001401494S00			

SOL 3899 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Guainia

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	3899MH0001900011401500C00	1500	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	3899MH0002990011401502C00	1502	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3899MH0002270001401561R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3899MH0002270001401562S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	3899MH0002990011401512C00	1512	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3899MH0002270001401559R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3899MH0002270001401560S00	
mhl100335	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 2 cm													
	3899MH0003350011401522C00	1522	14706	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3899MH0002270001401557R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3899MH0002270001401558S00	

target named Mocambo

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm													
	3899MH0001900011401532C00	1532	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	3899MH0003080011401534C00	1534	14166	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3899MH0002270001401555R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3899MH0002270001401556S00	
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	3899MH0003080011401544C00	1544	14180	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3899MH0002270001401553R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3899MH0002270001401554S00	

UPDATED: 28_July_2023

SOL 3900 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Porta_Walter – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3900MH0001900011401564C00	1564	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3900MH0001680011401566C00	1566	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3901MH0002270001401625R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3901MH0002270001401626S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3900MH0001680011401576C00	1576	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3901MH0002270001401623R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3901MH0002270001401624S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3900MH0007430011401586C00	1586	15160	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3901MH0002270001401621R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3901MH0002270001401622S00

target named Purace

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3900MH0001900011401596C00	1596	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3900MH0001680011401598C00	1598	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3901MH0002270001401619R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3901MH0002270001401620S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3900MH0001680011401608C00	1608	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3901MH0002270001401617R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3901MH0002270001401618S00

UPDATED: 31_July_2023

SOL 3902 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Jamari – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3902MH0001900011401628C00	1628	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3902MH0001680011401630C00	1630	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3904MH0001930001401663R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3904MH0001930001401664S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3902MH0001680011401640C00	1640	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3904MH0001930001401661R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3904MH0001930001401662S00	
mhl10743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	3902MH0007430011401650C00	1650	15119	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3904MH0001930001401659R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3904MH0001930001401660S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3779–3902 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3780, 3796, 3798, 3800, 3803, 3807, 3810, 3812, 3817, 3819, 3821, 3834, 3837, 3839, 3845, 3851, 3853, 3858, 3859, 3862, 3866, 3871, 3873, 3877, 3880, 3885, 3887, 3889, 3892, 3895, 3898, 3899, 3900, 3902**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus

position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the

second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the

motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Capanapro - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0002990011304538C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304609R00	4609	MOTOR COUNT:		13957	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304610S00	4610	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3781	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0002990021304539C00	4539	13813	8.25	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	255	1
3780MH0002990021304540C00	4540	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
3780MH0002990021304541C00	4541	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
3780MH0002990021304542C00	4542	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
3780MH0002990021304543C00	4543	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3780MH0002990021304544C00	4544	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
3780MH0002990021304545C00	4545	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3780MH0002990021304546C00	4546	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Capanapro - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0002990011304548C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304607R00	4607	MOTOR COUNT:		13969	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304608S00	4608	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3781	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0002990021304549C00	4549	13825	8.15	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
3780MH0002990021304550C00	4550	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3780MH0002990021304551C00	4551	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3780MH0002990021304552C00	4552	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3780MH0002990021304553C00	4553	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3780MH0002990021304554C00	4554	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3780MH0002990021304555C00	4555	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3780MH0002990021304556C00	4556	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Capanapro - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0001740011304558C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304605R00	4605	MOTOR COUNT:		14604	RANGE (cm):	4.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304606S00	4606	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00174	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3781	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0001740021304559C00	4559	14364	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	255	1
3780MH0001740021304560C00	4560	14424	4.70	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	223	2
3780MH0001740021304561C00	4561	14484	4.48	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	191	3
3780MH0001740021304562C00	4562	14544	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	159	4
3780MH0001740021304563C00	4563	14604	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	127	5
3780MH0001740021304564C00	4564	14664	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	95	6
3780MH0001740021304565C00	4565	14724	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3780MH0001740021304566C00	4566	14784	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Amanau - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0002990011304570C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304603R00	4603	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304604S00	4604	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3781	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0002990021304571C00	4571	13858	7.88	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3780MH0002990021304572C00	4572	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3780MH0002990021304573C00	4573	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3780MH0002990021304574C00	4574	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3780MH0002990021304575C00	4575	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3780MH0002990021304576C00	4576	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3780MH0002990021304577C00	4577	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3780MH0002990021304578C00	4578	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Amanau - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0002990011304580C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304601R00	4601	MOTOR COUNT:	14013	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304602S00	4602	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3781			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0002990021304581C00	4581	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3780MH0002990021304582C00	4582	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3780MH0002990021304583C00	4583	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3780MH0002990021304584C00	4584	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3780MH0002990021304585C00	4585	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3780MH0002990021304586C00	4586	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3780MH0002990021304587C00	4587	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3780MH0002990021304588C00	4588	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3870 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Amanau - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3780MH0007960011304590C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3781MH0001630001304599R00	4599	MOTOR COUNT:	15136	RANGE (cm):	2.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3781MH0001630001304600S00	4600	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00796	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Mar-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3780	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3781			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3780MH0007960021304591C00	4591	14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3780MH0007960021304592C00	4592	15010	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3780MH0007960021304593C00	4593	15052	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3780MH0007960021304594C00	4594	15094	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3780MH0007960021304595C00	4595	15136	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3780MH0007960021304596C00	4596	15178	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
3780MH0007960021304597C00	4597	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3780MH0007960021304598C00	4598	15262	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 26_October_2023

SOL 3796 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarilandia - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3796MH0001820011304614C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3796MH0001930001304647R00	4647	MOTOR COUNT:		14035	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3796MH0001930001304648S00	4648	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3796	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3796	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3796MH0001820021304615C00	4615	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3796MH0001820021304616C00	4616	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3796MH0001820021304617C00	4617	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3796MH0001820021304618C00	4618	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3796MH0001820021304619C00	4619	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3796MH0001820021304620C00	4620	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3796MH0001820021304621C00	4621	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3796MH0001820021304622C00	4622	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_October_2023

SOL 3796 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarilandia - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3796MH0001820011304624C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3796MH0001930001304645R00	4645	MOTOR COUNT:		14038	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3796MH0001930001304646S00	4646	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3796	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3796	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3796MH0001820021304625C00	4625	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3796MH0001820021304626C00	4626	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3796MH0001820021304627C00	4627	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3796MH0001820021304628C00	4628	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3796MH0001820021304629C00	4629	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3796MH0001820021304630C00	4630	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3796MH0001820021304631C00	4631	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3796MH0001820021304632C00	4632	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_October_2023

SOL 3796 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Tarilandia – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3796MH0001840011304634C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3796MH0001930001304643R00		4643		MOTOR COUNT:		14762		RANGE (cm): 3.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3796MH0001930001304644S00		4644		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		11-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36			ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3796		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 3796	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3796MH0001840021304635C00	4635	14618	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	255	1		
3796MH0001840021304636C00	4636	14654	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	223	2		
3796MH0001840021304637C00	4637	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	191	3		
3796MH0001840021304638C00	4638	14726	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	159	4		
3796MH0001840021304639C00	4639	14762	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	127	5		
3796MH0001840021304640C00	4640	14798	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	95	6		
3796MH0001840021304641C00	4641	14834	3.42	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	63	7		
3796MH0001840021304642C00	4642	14870	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantario – mosaic position 1 of 6 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011304650C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904761R00		4761		MOTOR COUNT:		13998		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904762S00		4762		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021304651C00	4651	13854	7.91	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021304652C00	4652	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2		
3798MH0002990021304653C00	4653	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021304654C00	4654	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021304655C00	4655	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021304656C00	4656	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6		
3798MH0002990021304657C00	4657	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021304658C00	4658	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantario – mosaic position 2 of 6 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011304660C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904759R00		4759		MOTOR COUNT:		14011		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904760S00		4760		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021304661C00	4661	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021304662C00	4662	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2		
3798MH0002990021304663C00	4663	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021304664C00	4664	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021304665C00	4665	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021204666C00	4666	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6		
3798MH0002990021204667C00	4667	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021204668C00	4668	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantarrio - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011204670C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904757R00		4757		MOTOR COUNT:		14021		RANGE (cm): 6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904758S00		4758		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021204671C00	4671	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021204672C00	4672	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2		
3798MH0002990021204673C00	4673	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021204674C00	4674	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021204675C00	4675	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021204676C00	4676	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
3798MH0002990021204677C00	4677	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021204678C00	4678	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantarrio - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011204680C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904755R00		4755		MOTOR COUNT:		14024		RANGE (cm): 6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904756S00		4756		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021204681C00	4681	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021204682C00	4682	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2		
3798MH0002990021204683C00	4683	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021204684C00	4684	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021204685C00	4685	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021204686C00	4686	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
3798MH0002990021204687C00	4687	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021204688C00	4688	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantarrio – mosaic position 5 of 6 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011204690C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904753R00		4753		MOTOR COUNT:		14008		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904754S00		4754		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021204691C00	4691	13864	7.83	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021204692C00	4692	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2		
3798MH0002990021204693C00	4693	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021104694C00	4694	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021104695C00	4695	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021104696C00	4696	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6		
3798MH0002990021104697C00	4697	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021104698C00	4698	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cantarrio – mosaic position 6 of 6 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0002990011104700C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904751R00		4751		MOTOR COUNT:		14000		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904752S00		4752		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0002990021104701C00	4701	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1		
3798MH0002990021104702C00	4702	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2		
3798MH0002990021104703C00	4703	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3		
3798MH0002990021104704C00	4704	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4		
3798MH0002990021104705C00	4705	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
3798MH0002990021104706C00	4706	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6		
3798MH0002990021104707C00	4707	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3798MH0002990021104708C00	4708	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cupixi - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0007230011104713C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3799MH0005360000904749R00	4749	MOTOR COUNT:	13988	RANGE (cm):	6.9			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3799MH0005360000904750S00	4750	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3798	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3799			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3798MH0007230031104715C00	4715	13844	7.99	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3798MH0007230031104716C00	4716	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3798MH0007230031104717C00	4717	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3798MH0007230031104718C00	4718	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3798MH0007230031104719C00	4719	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3798MH0007230031104720C00	4720	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3798MH0007230031104721C00	4721	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3798MH0007230031104722C00	4722	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cupixi - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0007230011104724C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3799MH0005360000904747R00	4747	MOTOR COUNT:	13985	RANGE (cm):	6.9			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3799MH0005360000904748S00	4748	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3798	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3799			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3798MH0007230031104726C00	4726	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
3798MH0007230031104727C00	4727	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
3798MH0007230031104728C00	4728	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3798MH0007230031104729C00	4729	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3798MH0007230031104730C00	4730	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3798MH0007230031104731C00	4731	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3798MH0007230031104732C00	4732	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3798MH0007230031104733C00	4733	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3798 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cupixi – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3798MH0007940011104735C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3799MH0005360000904745R00		4745		MOTOR COUNT:		14828		RANGE (cm): 3.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3799MH0005360000904746S00		4746		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00794		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		13-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3798		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3799	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3798MH0007940031004737C00	4737	14636	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	255	1		
3798MH0007940030904738C00	4738	14684	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	223	2		
3798MH0007940030904739C00	4739	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	191	3		
3798MH0007940030904740C00	4740	14780	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	159	4		
3798MH0007940030904741C00	4741	14828	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	127	5		
3798MH0007940030904742C00	4742	14876	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	95	6		
3798MH0007940030904743C00	4743	14924	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	63	7		
3798MH0007940030904744C00	4744	14972	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0004590010804766C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000604853R00	4853	MOTOR COUNT:		14222	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000604854S00	4854	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00459	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		96	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0004590020804767C00	3767	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3800MH0004590020804768C00	3768	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3800MH0004590020804769C00	3769	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
3800MH0004590020804770C00	3770	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
3800MH0004590020804771C00	3771	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3800MH0004590020804772C00	3772	14318	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	95	6
3800MH0004590020804773C00	3773	14414	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	63	7
3800MH0004590020804774C00	3774	14510	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - ~4 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0004590010804776C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000604851R00	4851	MOTOR COUNT:		14184	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000604852S00	4852	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00459	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		96	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0004590020804777C00	4777	13800	8.37	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1
3800MH0004590020804778C00	4778	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3800MH0004590020804779C00	4779	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3800MH0004590020804780C00	4780	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
3800MH0004590020804781C00	4781	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
3800MH0004590020804782C00	4782	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	95	6
3800MH0004590020804783C00	4783	14376	4.89	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	63	7
3800MH0004590020804784C00	4784	14472	4.52	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lorenzo - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0007630010804789C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000704849R00	4849	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000604850S00	4850	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0007630030804791C00	4791	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3800MH0007630030804792C00	4792	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3800MH0007630030804793C00	4793	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3800MH0007630030804794C00	4794	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3800MH0007630030804795C00	4795	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3800MH0007630030804796C00	4796	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3800MH0007630030804797C00	4797	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3800MH0007630030804798C00	4798	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lorenzo - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0007630010804800C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000704847R00	4847	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000704848S00	4848	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0007630030804802C00	4802	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3800MH0007630030804803C00	4803	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3800MH0007630030804804C00	4804	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3800MH0007630030804805C00	4805	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3800MH0007630030804806C00	4806	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3800MH0007630030804807C00	4807	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3800MH0007630030804808C00	4808	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3800MH0007630030804809C00	4809	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lorenzo - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0007940010804817C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000704845R00	4845	MOTOR COUNT:		15063	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000704846S00	4846	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00794	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0007940030804819C00	4819	14871	3.33	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1
3800MH0007940030804820C00	4820	14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
3800MH0007940030804821C00	4821	14967	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
3800MH0007940030804822C00	4822	15015	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	159	4
3800MH0007940030804823C00	4823	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
3800MH0007940030804824C00	4824	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
3800MH0007940030804825C00	4825	15159	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
3800MH0007940030804826C00	4826	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 29_June_2023

SOL 3800 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lorenzo - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3800MH0007630010804828C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3801MH0001630000704843R00	4843	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3801MH0001630000704844S00	4844	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00763	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Apr-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3800	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3801	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3800MH0007630030704830C00	4830	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3800MH0007630030704831C00	4831	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3800MH0007630030704832C00	4832	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3800MH0007630030704833C00	4833	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3800MH0007630030704834C00	4834	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3800MH0007630030704835C00	4835	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3800MH0007630030704836C00	4836	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3800MH0007630030704837C00	4837	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_October_2023

SOL 3803 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		ChemCam RWEB window – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3803MH0005200011400002C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3803MH0007680001400031R00	31	MOTOR COUNT:		13100	RANGE (cm):	22.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3803MH0007680001400032S00	32	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00520	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00768	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3803	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3803	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 16
				NEAR	FAR				
3803MH0005200021400003C00	3	12908	35.11	-3.0	3.6	130.5	11.7	n/a	1
3803MH0005200021400004C00	4	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	n/a	2
3803MH0005200021400005C00	5	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	255	3
3803MH0005200021400006C00	6	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	223	4
3803MH0005200021400007C00	7	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	191	5
3803MH0005200021400008C00	8	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	159	6
3803MH0005200021400009C00	9	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	127	7
3803MH0005200021400010C00	10	13076	23.33	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	95	8
3803MH0005200021400011C00	11	13100	22.22	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	63	9
3803MH0005200021400012C00	12	13124	21.20	-1.2	1.3	81.5	4.2	31	10
3803MH0005200021400013C00	13	13148	20.26	-1.1	1.1	78.2	3.9	n/a	11
3803MH0005200021400014C00	14	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	n/a	12
3803MH0005200021400015C00	15	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	n/a	13
3803MH0005200021400016C00	16	13220	17.84	-0.8	0.9	69.7	3.0	n/a	14
3803MH0005200021400017C00	17	13244	17.14	-0.8	0.8	67.2	2.8	n/a	15
3803MH0005200021400018C00	18	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	n/a	16

UPDATED: 26_October_2023

SOL 3803 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		ChemCam RWEB window – focused on internal hardware – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3803MH0005200041400020C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3803MH0007680001400029R00	29	MOTOR COUNT:		12990	RANGE (cm):		28.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3803MH0007680001400030S00	30	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00520	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00768	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3803	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3803	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3803MH0005200051400021C00	21	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	255	1
3803MH0005200051400022C00	22	12918	34.11	-2.9	3.4	127.0	11.1	223	2
3803MH0005200051400023C00	23	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	191	3
3803MH0005200051400024C00	24	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	159	4
3803MH0005200051400025C00	25	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	127	5
3803MH0005200051400026C00	26	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	95	6
3803MH0005200051400027C00	27	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	63	7
3803MH0005200051400028C00	28	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	31	8

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SOL 3807 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Floresta - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3807MH0001820011400036C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3808MH0002270001400095R00	95	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3808MH0002270001400096S00	96	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3807	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3808		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3807MH0001820021400037C00	37	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3807MH0001820021400038C00	38	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3807MH0001820021400039C00	39	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3807MH0001820021400040C00	40	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3807MH0001820021400041C00	41	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3807MH0001820021400042C00	42	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3807MH0001820021400043C00	43	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3807MH0001820021400044C00	44	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3807 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Floresta - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3807MH0001820011400046C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3808MH0002270001400093R00	93	MOTOR COUNT:		13991	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3808MH0002270001400094S00	94	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3807	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3808		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3807MH0001820021400047C00	47	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3807MH0001820021400048C00	48	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3807MH0001820021400049C00	49	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3807MH0001820021400050C00	50	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3807MH0001820021400051C00	51	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3807MH0001820021400052C00	52	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3807MH0001820021400053C00	53	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3807MH0001820021400054C00	54	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3807 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Floresta - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3807MH0003370011400056C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3808MH0002270001400091R00	91	MOTOR COUNT:		14650	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3808MH0002270001400092S00	92	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00337	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3807	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3808	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3807MH0003370021400057C00	57	14482	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	255	1
3807MH0003370021400058C00	58	14524	4.34	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	223	2
3807MH0003370021400059C00	59	14566	4.20	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	191	3
3807MH0003370021400060C00	60	14608	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3807MH0003370021400061C00	61	14650	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	127	5
3807MH0003370021400062C00	62	14692	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	95	6
3807MH0003370021400063C00	63	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7
3807MH0003370021400064C00	64	14776	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 3807 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Calama - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3807MH0002990011400068C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3808MH0002270001400089R00	89	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3808MH0002270001400090S00	90	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3807	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3808	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3807MH0002990021400069C00	69	13843	8.00	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
3807MH0002990021400070C00	70	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3807MH0002990021400071C00	71	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3807MH0002990021400072C00	72	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3807MH0002990021400073C00	73	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3807MH0002990021400074C00	74	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3807MH0002990021400075C00	75	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3807MH0002990021400076C00	76	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3807 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Calama - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3807MH0002990011400078C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3808MH0002270001400087R00	87	MOTOR COUNT:		13974	RANGE (cm):		7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3808MH0002270001400088S00	88	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3807		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3808	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
3807MH0002990021400079C00	79	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1	
3807MH0002990021400080C00	80	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2	
3807MH0002990021400081C00	81	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3	
3807MH0002990021400082C00	82	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4	
3807MH0002990021400083C00	83	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5	
3807MH0002990021400084C00	84	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6	
3807MH0002990021400085C00	85	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7	
3807MH0002990021400086C00	86	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8	

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SOL 3810 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Anortosito_Repartimento - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3810MH0001680011400100C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3810MH0001930001400133R00	133	MOTOR COUNT:		14055	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3810MH0001930001400134S00	134	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3810	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3810	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3810MH0001680021400101C00	101	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
3810MH0001680021400102C00	102	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
3810MH0001680021400103C00	103	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
3810MH0001680021400104C00	104	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
3810MH0001680021400105C00	105	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
3810MH0001680021400106C00	106	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
3810MH0001680021400107C00	107	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3810MH0001680021400108C00	108	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3810 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Anortosito_Repartimento - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3810MH0001680011400110C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3810MH0001930001400131R00	131	MOTOR COUNT:		14059	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3810MH0001930001400132S00	132	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3810	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3810	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3810MH0001680021400111C00	111	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
3810MH0001680021400112C00	112	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
3810MH0001680021400113C00	113	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	191	3
3810MH0001680021400114C00	114	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
3810MH0001680021400115C00	115	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
3810MH0001680021400116C00	116	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
3810MH0001680021400117C00	117	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3810MH0001680021400118C00	118	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3810 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Anortosito_Repartimento - after DRT - ~5 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3810MH0007960011400120C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3810MH0001930001400129R00		129		MOTOR COUNT:		15290		RANGE (cm): 2.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3810MH0001930001400130S00		130		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		25-Apr-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3810		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 3810		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3810MH0007960021400121C00	121	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	255	1		
3810MH0007960021400122C00	122	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	223	2		
3810MH0007960021400123C00	123	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	191	3		
3810MH0007960021400124C00	124	15248	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	159	4		
3810MH0007960021400125C00	125	15290	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	127	5		
3810MH0007960021400126C00	126	15332	2.42	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	95	6		
3810MH0007960021400127C00	127	15374	2.36	0.0	0.1	15.2	0.2	63	7		
3810MH0007960021400128C00	128	15416	2.30	0.0	0.1	15.0	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 3812 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Armero - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3812MH0001730011400138C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3812MH0001930001400171R00	171	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3812MH0001930001400172S00	172	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3812	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3812	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3812MH0001730021400139C00	139	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3812MH0001730021400140C00	140	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3812MH0001730021400141C00	141	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3812MH0001730021400142C00	142	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3812MH0001730021400143C00	143	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3812MH0001730021400144C00	144	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3812MH0001730021400145C00	145	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3812MH0001730021400146C00	146	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3812 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Armero - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3812MH0001730011400148C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3812MH0001930001400169R00	169	MOTOR COUNT:		14013	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3812MH0001930001400170S00	170	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3812	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3812	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3812MH0001730021400149C00	149	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3812MH0001730021400150C00	150	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3812MH0001730021400151C00	151	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3812MH0001730021400152C00	152	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3812MH0001730021400153C00	153	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3812MH0001730021400154C00	154	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3812MH0001730021400155C00	155	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3812MH0001730021400156C00	156	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3812 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Armero - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3812MH0003020011400158C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3812MH0001930001400167R00	167	MOTOR COUNT:		14713	RANGE (cm):		3.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3812MH0001930001400168S00	168	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Apr-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3812		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3812
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3812MH0003020021400159C00	159	14593	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
3812MH0003020021400160C00	160	14623	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2
3812MH0003020021400161C00	161	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	191	3
3812MH0003020021400162C00	162	14683	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	159	4
3812MH0003020021400163C00	163	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
3812MH0003020021400164C00	164	14743	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	95	6
3812MH0003020021400165C00	165	14773	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
3812MH0003020021400166C00	166	14803	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

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SOL 3817 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - before DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3817MH0001730011400178C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3818MH0001930001400213R00		213		MOTOR COUNT:		14013		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3818MH0001930001400214S00		214		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3817		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3818	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3817MH0001730021400179C00	179	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1		
3817MH0001730021400180C00	180	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2		
3817MH0001730021400181C00	181	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
3817MH0001730021400182C00	182	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
3817MH0001730021400183C00	183	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5		
3817MH0001730021400184C00	184	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6		
3817MH0001730021400185C00	185	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3817MH0001730021400186C00	186	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3817 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - before DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3817MH0001730011400188C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3818MH0001930001400211R00		211		MOTOR COUNT:		14011		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3818MH0001930001400212S00		212		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3817		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3818	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3817MH0001730021400189C00	189	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1		
3817MH0001730021400190C00	190	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2		
3817MH0001730021400191C00	191	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3		
3817MH0001730021400192C00	192	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
3817MH0001730021400193C00	193	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5		
3817MH0001730021400194C00	194	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6		
3817MH0001730021400195C00	195	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3817MH0001730021400196C00	196	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3817 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - before DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3817MH0001730011400198C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3818MH0001930001400209R00	209	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3818MH0001930001400210S00	210	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3817	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3818	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3817MH0001730021400199C00	199	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3817MH0001730021400200C00	200	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3817MH0001730021400201C00	201	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3817MH0001730021400202C00	202	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3817MH0001730021400203C00	203	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3817MH0001730021400204C00	204	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3817MH0001730021400205C00	205	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3817MH0001730021400206C00	206	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3819 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3819MH0001820011400218C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3819MH0001530001400263R00	263	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3819MH0001530001400264S00	264	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3819	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3819	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3819MH0001820021400219C00	219	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3819MH0001820021400220C00	220	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3819MH0001820021400221C00	221	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3819MH0001820021400222C00	222	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3819MH0001820021400223C00	223	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3819MH0001820021400224C00	224	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3819MH0001820021400225C00	225	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3819MH0001820021400226C00	226	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3819 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3819MH0001820011400228C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3819MH0001530001400261R00	261	MOTOR COUNT:		14012	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3819MH0001530001400262S00	262	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3819	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3819	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3819MH0001820021400229C00	229	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3819MH0001820021400230C00	230	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3819MH0001820021400231C00	231	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3819MH0001820021400232C00	232	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3819MH0001820021400233C00	233	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3819MH0001820021400234C00	234	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3819MH0001820021400235C00	235	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3819MH0001820021400236C00	236	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3819 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3819MH0004260011400238C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3819MH0001530001400259R00	259		MOTOR COUNT:		15125	RANGE (cm):	2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3819MH0001530001400260S00	260		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3819	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3819	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3819MH0004260021400239C00	239	14933	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
3819MH0004260021400240C00	240	14981	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	223	2
3819MH0004260021400241C00	241	15029	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
3819MH0004260021400242C00	242	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3819MH0004260021400243C00	243	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3819MH0004260021400244C00	244	15173	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
3819MH0004260021400245C00	245	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3819MH0004260021400246C00	246	15269	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

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SOL 3819 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ubajara - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3819MH0001820011400248C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3819MH0001530001400257R00	257		MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3819MH0001530001400258S00	258		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3819	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3819	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3819MH0001820021400249C00	249	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3819MH0001820021400250C00	250	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3819MH0001820021400251C00	251	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3819MH0001820021400252C00	252	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3819MH0001820021400253C00	253	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3819MH0001820021400254C00	254	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3819MH0001820021400255C00	255	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3819MH0001820021400256C00	256	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3821 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ilha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3821MH0001520011400270C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3821MH0002270001400329R00	329	MOTOR COUNT:		14105	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3821MH0002270001400330S00	330	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3821	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3821	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3821MH0001520021400271C00	271	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3821MH0001520021400272C00	272	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3821MH0001520021400273C00	273	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3821MH0001520021400274C00	274	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
3821MH0001520021400275C00	275	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3821MH0001520021400276C00	276	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	95	6
3821MH0001520021400277C00	277	14201	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
3821MH0001520021400278C00	278	14249	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3821 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ilha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3821MH0001520011400280C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3821MH0002270001400327R00	327	MOTOR COUNT:		14106	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3821MH0002270001400328S00	328	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3821	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3821	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3821MH0001520021400281C00	281	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3821MH0001520021400282C00	282	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3821MH0001520021400283C00	283	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3821MH0001520021400284C00	284	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
3821MH0001520021400285C00	285	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3821MH0001520021400286C00	286	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	95	6
3821MH0001520021400287C00	287	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
3821MH0001520021400288C00	288	14250	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3821 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ilha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3821MH0001520011400290C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3821MH0002270001400325R00		325		MOTOR COUNT:		14098		RANGE (cm): 6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400326S00		326		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		7-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3821		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3821	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3821MH0001520021400291C00	291	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1		
3821MH0001520021400292C00	292	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2		
3821MH0001520021400293C00	293	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3		
3821MH0001520021400294C00	294	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	159	4		
3821MH0001520021400295C00	295	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	127	5		
3821MH0001520021400296C00	296	14146	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	95	6		
3821MH0001520021400297C00	297	14194	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7		
3821MH0001520021400298C00	298	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8		

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SOL 3821 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bwesse_Kiiki - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3821MH0002990011400302C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3821MH0002270001400323R00		323		MOTOR COUNT:		14308		RANGE (cm): 5.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3821MH0002270001400324S00		324		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		7-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3821		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3821	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3821MH0002990021400303C00	303	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	255	1		
3821MH0002990021400304C00	304	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	223	2		
3821MH0002990021400305C00	305	14236	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	191	3		
3821MH0002990021400306C00	306	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	159	4		
3821MH0002990021400307C00	307	14308	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	127	5		
3821MH0002990021400308C00	308	14344	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	95	6		
3821MH0002990021400309C00	309	14380	4.88	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	63	7		
3821MH0002990021400310C00	310	14416	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8		

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SOL 3821 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bwesse_Kiiki - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3821MH0002990011400312C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3821MH0002270001400321R00	321	MOTOR COUNT:		14303	RANGE (cm):		5.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3821MH0002270001400322S00	322	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3821		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3821
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3821MH0002990021400313C00	313	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	255	1
3821MH0002990021400314C00	314	14195	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	223	2
3821MH0002990021400315C00	315	14231	5.54	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	191	3
3821MH0002990021400316C00	316	14267	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	159	4
3821MH0002990021400317C00	317	14303	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	127	5
3821MH0002990021400318C00	318	14339	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	95	6
3821MH0002990021400319C00	319	14375	4.90	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	63	7
3821MH0002990021400320C00	320	14411	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8

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SOL 3834 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Ubajara drill cuttings - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3834MH0001520011400340C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3834MH0002580001400349R00	349	MOTOR COUNT:		14067	RANGE (cm):		6.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3834MH0002580001400350S00	350	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	20-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00258		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3834		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3834
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3834MH0001520021400341C00	341	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3834MH0001520021400342C00	342	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3834MH0001520021400343C00	343	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3834MH0001520021400344C00	344	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3834MH0001520021400345C00	345	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
3834MH0001520021400346C00	346	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	95	6
3834MH0001520021400347C00	347	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3834MH0001520021400348C00	348	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3837 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Apetina - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3837MH0001820011400358C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3837MH0001930001400391R00	391	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3837MH0001930001400392S00	392	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-May-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3837	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3837		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3837MH0001820021400359C00	359	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3837MH0001820021400360C00	360	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3837MH0001820021400361C00	361	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3837MH0001820021400362C00	362	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3837MH0001820021400363C00	363	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3837MH0001820021400364C00	364	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3837MH0001820021400365C00	365	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3837MH0001820021400366C00	366	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3837 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Apetina - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3837MH0001820011400368C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3837MH0001930001400389R00	389	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3837MH0001930001400390S00	390	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-May-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3837	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3837		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3837MH0001820021400369C00	369	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3837MH0001820021400370C00	370	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3837MH0001820021400371C00	371	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3837MH0001820021400372C00	372	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3837MH0001820021400373C00	373	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3837MH0001820021400374C00	374	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3837MH0001820021400375C00	375	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3837MH0001820021400376C00	376	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3837 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Apetina - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3837MH0001840011400378C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3837MH0001930001400387R00		387		MOTOR COUNT:		14660		RANGE (cm): 3.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3837MH0001930001400388S00		388		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3837		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3837	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3837MH0001840021400379C00	379	14516	4.37	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	255	1		
3837MH0001840021400380C00	380	14552	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2		
3837MH0001840021400381C00	381	14588	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3		
3837MH0001840021400382C00	382	14624	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	159	4		
3837MH0001840021400383C00	383	14660	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	127	5		
3837MH0001840021400384C00	384	14696	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	95	6		
3837MH0001840021400385C00	385	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7		
3837MH0001840021400386C00	386	14768	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3837 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Apetina - after DRT - night imaging - group 2 LEDs on - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3837MH0008610031400395C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3838MH0002580001400410R00		410		MOTOR COUNT:		13987		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3838MH0002580001400411S00		411		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00861		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		23-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00258		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3837		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3838	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3837MH0008610101400402C00	402	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1		
3837MH0008610101400403C00	403	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2		
3837MH0008610101400404C00	404	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3		
3837MH0008610101400405C00	405	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4		
3837MH0008610101400406C00	406	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5		
3837MH0008610101400407C00	407	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6		
3837MH0008610101400408C00	408	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7		
3837MH0008610101400409C00	409	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3839 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zipaquira - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3839MH0001680011400415C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3839MH0001930001400448R00		448		MOTOR COUNT:		13999		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3839MH0001930001400449S00		449		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		25-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3839		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3839	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3839MH0001680021400416C00	416	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1		
3839MH0001680021400417C00	417	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2		
3839MH0001680021400418C00	418	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3		
3839MH0001680021400419C00	419	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
3839MH0001680021400420C00	420	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5		
3839MH0001680021400421C00	421	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
3839MH0001680021400422C00	422	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7		
3839MH0001680021400423C00	423	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3839 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zipaquira - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3839MH0001680011400425C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3839MH0001930001400446R00		446		MOTOR COUNT:		14002		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3839MH0001930001400447S00		447		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		25-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3839		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3839	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3839MH0001680021400426C00	426	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1		
3839MH0001680021400427C00	427	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2		
3839MH0001680021400428C00	428	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3		
3839MH0001680021400429C00	429	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4		
3839MH0001680021400430C00	430	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5		
3839MH0001680021400431C00	431	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6		
3839MH0001680021400432C00	432	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7		
3839MH0001680021400433C00	433	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3839 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zipaquira – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3839MH0007430011400435C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3839MH0001930001400444R00	444	MOTOR COUNT:		15108	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3839MH0001930001400445S00	445	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-May-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3839		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3839
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3839MH0007430021400436C00	436	14964	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	255	1
3839MH0007430021400437C00	437	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
3839MH0007430021400438C00	438	15036	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
3839MH0007430021400439C00	439	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
3839MH0007430021400440C00	440	15108	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3839MH0007430021400441C00	441	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
3839MH0007430021400442C00	442	15180	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3839MH0007430021400443C00	443	15216	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3845 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cujubim – after DRT – APXS spot 3 – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3845MH0001820011400457C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3846MH0002270001400514R00	514	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400515S00	515	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-May-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3845	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3846		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3845MH0001820021400458C00	458	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3845MH0001820021400459C00	459	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3845MH0001820021400460C00	460	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3845MH0001820021400461C00	461	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3845MH0001820021400462C00	462	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3845MH0001820021400463C00	463	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3845MH0001820021400464C00	464	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3845MH0001820021400465C00	465	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3845 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cujubim – after DRT – APXS spot 3 – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3845MH0001820011400467C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3846MH0002270001400512R00	512	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3846MH0002270001400513S00	513	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-May-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3845	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3846		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3845MH0001820021400468C00	468	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3845MH0001820021400469C00	469	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3845MH0001820021400470C00	470	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3845MH0001820021400471C00	471	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3845MH0001820021400472C00	472	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3845MH0001820021400473C00	473	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3845MH0001820021400474C00	474	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3845MH0001820021400475C00	475	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3845 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cujubim – after DRT – APXS spot 3 – ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3845MH0001840011400477C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3846MH0002270001400510R00		510		MOTOR COUNT:		14693		RANGE (cm): 3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3846MH0002270001400511S00		511		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		31-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3845		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3846	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3845MH0001840021400478C00	478	14549	4.25	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1		
3845MH0001840021400479C00	479	14585	4.13	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2		
3845MH0001840021400480C00	480	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3		
3845MH0001840021400481C00	481	14657	3.91	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4		
3845MH0001840021400482C00	482	14693	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5		
3845MH0001840021400483C00	483	14729	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6		
3845MH0001840021400484C00	484	14765	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7		
3845MH0001840021400485C00	485	14801	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3845 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cujubim – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3845MH0001820011400487C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3846MH0002270001400508R00		508		MOTOR COUNT:		13992		RANGE (cm): 6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3846MH0002270001400509S00		509		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		31-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3845		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3846	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3845MH0001820021400488C00	488	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1		
3845MH0001820021400489C00	489	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2		
3845MH0001820021400490C00	490	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3		
3845MH0001820021400491C00	491	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4		
3845MH0001820021400492C00	492	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5		
3845MH0001820021400493C00	493	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
3845MH0001820021400494C00	494	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7		
3845MH0001820021400495C00	495	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3845 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cujubim – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3845MH0001820011400497C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3846MH0002270001400506R00		506		MOTOR COUNT:		13997		RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3846MH0002270001400507S00		507		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		31-May-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3845		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3846		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3845MH0001820021400498C00	498	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1				
3845MH0001820021400499C00	499	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2				
3845MH0001820021400500C00	500	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3				
3845MH0001820021400501C00	501	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4				
3845MH0001820021400502C00	502	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5				
3845MH0001820021400503C00	503	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6				
3845MH0001820021400504C00	504	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7				
3845MH0001820021400505C00	505	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8				

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3851 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aporema - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3851MH0001680011400519C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3851MH0001930001400552R00	552	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3851MH0001930001400553S00	553	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3851	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3851	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3851MH0001680021400520C00	520	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
3851MH0001680021400521C00	521	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3851MH0001680021400522C00	522	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3851MH0001680021400523C00	523	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3851MH0001680021400524C00	524	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3851MH0001680021400525C00	525	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3851MH0001680021400526C00	526	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3851MH0001680021400527C00	527	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3851 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aporema - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3851MH0001680011400529C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3851MH0001930001400550R00	550	MOTOR COUNT:		14033	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3851MH0001930001400551S00	551	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3851	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3851	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3851MH0001680021400530C00	530	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
3851MH0001680021400531C00	531	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
3851MH0001680021400532C00	532	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3851MH0001680021400533C00	533	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3851MH0001680021400534C00	534	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3851MH0001680021400535C00	535	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3851MH0001680021400536C00	536	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3851MH0001680021400537C00	537	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3851 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aporema – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff												
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3851MH0008480011400539C00								
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3851MH0001930001400548R00		548		MOTOR COUNT:		15200		RANGE (cm):		2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3851MH0001930001400549S00		549		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		7-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3851		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3851			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8					
				NEAR	FAR									
3851MH0008480021400540C00	540	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1					
3851MH0008480021400541C00	541	15128	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2					
3851MH0008480021400542C00	542	15152	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3					
3851MH0008480021400543C00	543	15176	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	159	4					
3851MH0008480021400544C00	544	15200	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5					
3851MH0008480021400545C00	545	15224	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6					
3851MH0008480021400546C00	546	15248	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7					
3851MH0008480021400547C00	547	15272	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8					

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3853 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Massaco - stereo-1 - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3853MH0008620011400555C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3853MH0008170001400607R00	607	MOTOR COUNT:		13050	RANGE (cm):	24.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3853MH0008170001400608S00	608	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00862	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00817	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3853	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3853		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3853MH0008620031400557C00	557	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	255	1
3853MH0008620031400558C00	558	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	223	2
3853MH0008620031400559C00	559	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	191	3
3853MH0008620031400560C00	560	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	159	4
3853MH0008620031400561C00	561	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	127	5
3853MH0008620031400562C00	562	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	95	6
3853MH0008620031400563C00	563	13086	22.85	-1.3	1.5	87.3	4.9	63	7
3853MH0008620031400564C00	564	13104	22.04	-1.3	1.4	84.5	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3853 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Massaco - stereo-2 - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3853MH0008620011400566C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3853MH0008170001400605R00	605	MOTOR COUNT:		13048	RANGE (cm):	24.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3853MH0008170001400606S00	606	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00862	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00817	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3853	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3853		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3853MH0008620031400568C00	568	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	255	1
3853MH0008620031400569C00	569	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	223	2
3853MH0008620031400570C00	570	13012	26.83	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	191	3
3853MH0008620031400571C00	571	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	159	4
3853MH0008620031400572C00	572	13048	24.75	-1.6	1.7	94.0	5.8	127	5
3853MH0008620031400573C00	573	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	95	6
3853MH0008620031400574C00	574	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	63	7
3853MH0008620031400575C00	575	13102	22.13	-1.3	1.4	84.8	4.6	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3853 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Saul - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3853MH0007230011400580C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3853MH0008170001400603R00	603	MOTOR COUNT:		14226	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3853MH0008170001400604S00	604	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00817	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3853	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3853	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3853MH0007230031400582C00	582	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	255	1
3853MH0007230031400583C00	583	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	223	2
3853MH0007230031400584C00	584	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	191	3
3853MH0007230031400585C00	585	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
3853MH0007230031400586C00	586	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3853MH0007230031400587C00	587	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	95	6
3853MH0007230031400588C00	588	14298	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	63	7
3853MH0007230031400589C00	589	14334	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 10_July_2023

SOL 3853 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Saul - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3853MH0007230011400591C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3853MH0008170001400601R00	601	MOTOR COUNT:		14166	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3853MH0008170001400602S00	602	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00817	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3853	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3853	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3853MH0007230031400593C00	593	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	255	1
3853MH0007230031400594C00	594	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
3853MH0007230031400595C00	595	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
3853MH0007230031400596C00	596	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	159	4
3853MH0007230031400597C00	597	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
3853MH0007230031400598C00	598	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	95	6
3853MH0007230031400599C00	599	14238	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
3853MH0007230031400600C00	600	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 16_June_2023

SOL 3858 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Terebito - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3858MH0001680011400615C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3858MH0001930001400650R00	650	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3858MH0001930001400651S00	651	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3858	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3858	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3858MH0001680021400616C00	616	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3858MH0001680021400617C00	617	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3858MH0001680021400618C00	618	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3858MH0001680021400619C00	619	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3858MH0001680021400620C00	620	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3858MH0001680021400621C00	621	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3858MH0001680021400622C00	622	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3858MH0001680021400623C00	623	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_June_2023

SOL 3858 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Terebito - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3858MH0001680011400625C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3858MH0001930001400648R00	648	MOTOR COUNT:		14005	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3858MH0001930001400649S00	649	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3858	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3858	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3858MH0001680021400626C00	626	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3858MH0001680021400627C00	627	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3858MH0001680021400628C00	628	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3858MH0001680021400629C00	629	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3858MH0001680021400630C00	630	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3858MH0001680021400631C00	631	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3858MH0001680021400632C00	632	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3858MH0001680021400633C00	633	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_June_2023

SOL 3858 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Terebito – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff								
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3858MH0001930001400646R00		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3858MH0007430011400635C00			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3858MH0001930001400647S00		646	MOTOR COUNT:		15144	RANGE (cm):	2.7	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		14-Jun-23		647	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3858	MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES		CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
					NEAR	FAR				
3858MH0007430021400636C00		636	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3858MH0007430021400637C00		637	15036	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3858MH0007430021400638C00		638	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3858MH0007430021400639C00		639	15108	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3858MH0007430021400640C00		640	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3858MH0007430021400641C00		641	15180	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
3858MH0007430021400642C00		642	15216	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3858MH0007430021400643C00		643	15252	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Madeira - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0001820011400677C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3860MH0001630001400747R00	747	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3860MH0001630001400748S00	748	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3859	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3859MH0001820021400678C00	678	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3859MH0001820021400679C00	679	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3859MH0001820021400680C00	680	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3859MH0001820021400681C00	681	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3859MH0001820021400682C00	682	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3859MH0001820021400683C00	683	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3859MH0001820021400684C00	684	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3859MH0001820021400685C00	685	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Madeira - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0001820011400687C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3860MH0001630001400745R00	745	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3860MH0001630001400746S00	746	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3859	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3859MH0001820021400688C00	688	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3859MH0001820021400689C00	689	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3859MH0001820021400690C00	690	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3859MH0001820021400691C00	691	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3859MH0001820021400692C00	692	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3859MH0001820021400693C00	693	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3859MH0001820021400694C00	694	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3859MH0001820021400695C00	695	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Madeira – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0007430011400697C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3860MH0001630001400743R00		743		MOTOR COUNT:		15086		RANGE (cm):		2.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400744S00		744		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3859		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3859MH0007430021400698C00	698	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1				
3859MH0007430021400699C00	699	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2				
3859MH0007430021400700C00	700	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3				
3859MH0007430021400701C00	701	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4				
3859MH0007430021400702C00	702	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5				
3859MH0007430021400703C00	703	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6				
3859MH0007430021400704C00	704	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7				
3859MH0007430021400705C00	705	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8				

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Macapa – ~25 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0006780011400707C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3860MH0001630001400741R00		741		MOTOR COUNT:		13006		RANGE (cm):		27.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3860MH0001630001400742S00		742		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00678		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		15-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3859		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3859MH0006780031400709C00	709	12910	34.90	-3.0	3.6	129.8	11.6	255	1				
3859MH0006780031400710C00	710	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	223	2				
3859MH0006780031400711C00	711	12958	30.61	-2.3	2.7	114.7	8.9	191	3				
3859MH0006780031400712C00	712	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	159	4				
3859MH0006780031400713C00	713	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	127	5				
3859MH0006780031400714C00	714	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	95	6				
3859MH0006780031400715C00	715	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	63	7				
3859MH0006780031400716C00	716	13078	23.23	-1.4	1.5	88.7	5.1	31	8				

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Macapa – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0003060011400718C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3860MH0001630001400739R00	739	MOTOR COUNT:		13958	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3860MH0001630001400740S00	740	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3859	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3859MH0003060021400719C00	719	13742	8.91	-0.3	0.2	38.3	0.8	255	1
3859MH0003060021400720C00	720	13796	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
3859MH0003060021400721C00	721	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
3859MH0003060021400722C00	722	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	159	4
3859MH0003060021400723C00	723	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3859MH0003060021400724C00	724	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3859MH0003060021400725C00	725	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3859MH0003060021400726C00	726	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3859 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Macapa – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3859MH0003060011400728C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3860MH0001630001400737R00	737	MOTOR COUNT:		13976	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3860MH0001630001400738S00	738	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3859	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3860	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3859MH0003060021400729C00	729	13760	8.73	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	255	1
3859MH0003060021400730C00	730	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
3859MH0003060021400731C00	731	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	191	3
3859MH0003060021400732C00	732	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
3859MH0003060021400733C00	733	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3859MH0003060021400734C00	734	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3859MH0003060021400735C00	735	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3859MH0003060021400736C00	736	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Surpresa - before DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0001820011400752C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400823R00	823	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400824S00	824	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0001820021400753C00	753	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3862MH0001820021400754C00	754	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3862MH0001820021400755C00	755	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3862MH0001820021400756C00	756	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3862MH0001820021400757C00	757	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3862MH0001820021400758C00	758	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3862MH0001820021400759C00	759	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3862MH0001820021400760C00	760	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Surpresa - before DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0001820011400762C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400821R00	821	MOTOR COUNT:		14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400822S00	822	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0001820021400763C00	763	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3862MH0001820021400764C00	764	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3862MH0001820021400765C00	765	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3862MH0001820021400766C00	766	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3862MH0001820021400767C00	767	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3862MH0001820021400768C00	768	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3862MH0001820021400769C00	769	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3862MH0001820021400770C00	770	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Surpresa - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0001820011400774C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400819R00	819	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400820S00	820	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0001820021400775C00	775	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3862MH0001820021400776C00	776	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3862MH0001820021400777C00	777	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3862MH0001820021400778C00	778	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3862MH0001820021400779C00	779	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3862MH0001820021400780C00	780	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3862MH0001820021400781C00	781	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3862MH0001820021400782C00	782	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Surpresa - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0001820011400784C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400817R00	817	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400818S00	818	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0001820021400785C00	785	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3862MH0001820021400786C00	786	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3862MH0001820021400787C00	787	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3862MH0001820021400788C00	788	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3862MH0001820021400789C00	789	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3862MH0001820021400790C00	790	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3862MH0001820021400791C00	791	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3862MH0001820021400792C00	792	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Surpresa – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0007430011400794C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400815R00	815	MOTOR COUNT:		15073	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400816S00	816	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0007430021400795C00	795	14929	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
3862MH0007430021400796C00	796	14965	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
3862MH0007430021400797C00	797	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
3862MH0007430021400798C00	798	15037	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
3862MH0007430021400799C00	799	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
3862MH0007430021400800C00	800	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
3862MH0007430021400801C00	801	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
3862MH0007430021400802C00	802	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 20_June_2023

SOL 3862 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Surpresa – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3862MH0001820011400804C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3864MH0001630001400813R00	813	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3864MH0001630001400814S00	814	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	18-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3862	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3864	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3862MH0001820021400805C00	805	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3862MH0001820021400806C00	806	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3862MH0001820021400807C00	807	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3862MH0001820021400808C00	808	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3862MH0001820021400809C00	809	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3862MH0001820021400810C00	810	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3862MH0001820021400811C00	811	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3862MH0001820021400812C00	812	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_July_2023

SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Feneos – mosaic position 1 of 5 – ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0002990011400828C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400935R00	935	MOTOR COUNT:		14246	RANGE (cm):	5.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400936S00	936	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0002990021400829C00	829	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	255	1
3866MH0002990021400830C00	830	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	223	2
3866MH0002990021400831C00	831	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	191	3
3866MH0002990021400832C00	832	14210	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	159	4
3866MH0002990021400833C00	833	14246	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	127	5
3866MH0002990021400834C00	834	14282	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	95	6
3866MH0002990021400835C00	835	14318	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
3866MH0002990021400836C00	836	14354	4.99	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Feneos – mosaic position 2 of 5 – ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0002990011400838C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400933R00	933	MOTOR COUNT:		14217	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400934S00	934	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0002990021400839C00	839	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	255	1
3866MH0002990021400840C00	840	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
3866MH0002990021400841C00	841	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
3866MH0002990021400842C00	842	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
3866MH0002990021400843C00	843	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3866MH0002990021400844C00	844	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
3866MH0002990021400845C00	845	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	63	7
3866MH0002990021400846C00	846	14325	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Feneos – mosaic position 3 of 5 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0002990011400848C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400931R00	931	MOTOR COUNT:		14105	RANGE (cm):	6.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400932S00	932	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0002990021400849C00	849	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
3866MH0002990021400850C00	850	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	223	2
3866MH0002990021400851C00	851	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3866MH0002990021400852C00	852	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	159	4
3866MH0002990021400853C00	853	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3866MH0002990021400854C00	854	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
3866MH0002990021400855C00	855	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
3866MH0002990021400856C00	856	14213	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Feneos – mosaic position 4 of 5 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0002990011400858C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400929R00	929	MOTOR COUNT:		14115	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400930S00	930	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0002990021400859C00	859	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3866MH0002990021400860C00	860	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	223	2
3866MH0002990021400861C00	861	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	191	3
3866MH0002990021400862C00	862	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4
3866MH0002990021400863C00	863	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3866MH0002990021400864C00	864	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	95	6
3866MH0002990021400865C00	865	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
3866MH0002990021400866C00	866	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Feneos – mosaic position 5 of 5 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0002990011400868C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400927R00	927	MOTOR COUNT:		14052	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400928S00	928	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0002990021400869C00	869	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3866MH0002990021400870C00	870	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3866MH0002990021400871C00	871	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3866MH0002990021400872C00	872	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3866MH0002990021400873C00	873	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
3866MH0002990021400874C00	874	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3866MH0002990021400875C00	875	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	63	7
3866MH0002990021400876C00	876	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3866 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kastria_Spring – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0001820011400880C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400925R00	925	MOTOR COUNT:		13979	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400926S00	926	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0001820021400881C00	881	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3866MH0001820021400882C00	882	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3866MH0001820021400883C00	883	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3866MH0001820021400884C00	884	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3866MH0001820021400885C00	885	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3866MH0001820021400886C00	886	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3866MH0001820021400887C00	887	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3866MH0001820021400888C00	888	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3866 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kastria_Spring - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0001820011400890C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3867MH0005360001400923R00		923		MOTOR COUNT:		13962		RANGE (cm):		7.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3867MH0005360001400924S00		924		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3866MH0001820021400891C00	891	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1				
3866MH0001820021400892C00	892	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2				
3866MH0001820021400893C00	893	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3				
3866MH0001820021400894C00	894	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4				
3866MH0001820021400895C00	895	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5				
3866MH0001820021400896C00	896	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6				
3866MH0001820021400897C00	897	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7				
3866MH0001820021400898C00	898	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8				

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SOL 3866 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kastria_Spring - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~2 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0003020011400900C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3867MH0005360001400921R00		921		MOTOR COUNT:		14640		RANGE (cm):		4.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3867MH0005360001400922S00		922		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3866MH0003020021400901C00	901	14520	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	255	1				
3866MH0003020021400902C00	902	14550	4.25	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	223	2				
3866MH0003020021400903C00	903	14580	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	191	3				
3866MH0003020021400904C00	904	14610	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4				
3866MH0003020021400905C00	905	14640	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5				
3866MH0003020021400906C00	906	14670	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	95	6				
3866MH0003020021400907C00	907	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	63	7				
3866MH0003020021400908C00	908	14730	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	31	8				

UPDATED: 05_July_2023

SOL 3866 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kastria_Spring - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3866MH0001820011400910C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3867MH0005360001400919R00	919	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3867MH0005360001400920S00	920	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3866	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3867	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3866MH0001820021400911C00	911	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3866MH0001820021400912C00	912	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3866MH0001820021400913C00	913	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3866MH0001820021400914C00	914	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3866MH0001820021400915C00	915	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3866MH0001820021400916C00	916	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3866MH0001820021400917C00	917	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3866MH0001820021400918C00	918	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3871 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lousoi - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3871MH0001820011400940C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3871MH0001930001400973R00	973	MOTOR COUNT:		13978	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3871MH0001930001400974S00	974	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3871	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3871	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3871MH0001820021400941C00	941	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3871MH0001820021400942C00	942	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3871MH0001820021400943C00	943	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3871MH0001820021400944C00	944	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3871MH0001820021400945C00	945	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3871MH0001820021400946C00	946	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3871MH0001820021400947C00	947	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3871MH0001820021400948C00	948	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3871 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lousoi - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3871MH0001820011400950C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3871MH0001930001400971R00	971	MOTOR COUNT:		13985	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3871MH0001930001400972S00	972	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jun-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3871	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3871	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3871MH0001820021400951C00	951	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3871MH0001820021400952C00	952	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3871MH0001820021400953C00	953	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3871MH0001820021400954C00	954	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3871MH0001820021400955C00	955	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3871MH0001820021400956C00	956	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3871MH0001820021400957C00	957	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3871MH0001820021400958C00	958	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3871 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lousoi - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff												
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3871MH0001760011400960C00								
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3871MH0001930001400969R00		969		MOTOR COUNT:		14638		RANGE (cm):		4.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3871MH0001930001400970S00		970		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00176		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jun-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			48			ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3871		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:			3871	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8					
				NEAR	FAR									
3871MH0001760021400961C00	961	14446	4.62	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	255	1					
3871MH0001760021400962C00	962	14494	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	223	2					
3871MH0001760021400963C00	963	14542	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	191	3					
3871MH0001760021400964C00	964	14590	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	159	4					
3871MH0001760021400965C00	965	14638	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	127	5					
3871MH0001760021400966C00	966	14686	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6					
3871MH0001760021400967C00	967	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7					
3871MH0001760021400968C00	968	14782	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8					

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3873 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Madero - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3873MH0001680011400978C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3873MH0002270001401037R00	1037	MOTOR COUNT:		14070	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3873MH0002270001401038S00	1038	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3873	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3873	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3873MH0001680021400979C00	979	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3873MH0001680021400980C00	980	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
3873MH0001680021400981C00	981	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3873MH0001680021400982C00	982	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3873MH0001680021400983C00	983	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	127	5
3873MH0001680021400984C00	984	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3873MH0001680021400985C00	985	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3873MH0001680021400986C00	986	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3873 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Madero - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3873MH0001680011400988C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3873MH0002270001401035R00	1035	MOTOR COUNT:		14053	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3873MH0002270001401036S00	1036	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3873	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3873	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3873MH0001680021400989C00	989	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
3873MH0001680021400990C00	990	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	223	2
3873MH0001680021400991C00	991	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
3873MH0001680021400992C00	992	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3873MH0001680021400993C00	993	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	127	5
3873MH0001680021400994C00	994	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
3873MH0001680021400995C00	995	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3873MH0001680021400996C00	996	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3873 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Madero - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3873MH0001840011400998C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3873MH0002270001401033R00	1033	MOTOR COUNT:	14808	RANGE (cm):	3.5			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3873MH0002270001401034S00	1034	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00184	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3873	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3873			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3873MH0001840021400999C00	999	14664	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	255	1
3873MH0001840021401000C00	1000	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	223	2
3873MH0001840021401001C00	1001	14736	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	191	3
3873MH0001840021401002C00	1002	14772	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	159	4
3873MH0001840021401003C00	1003	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	127	5
3873MH0001840021401004C00	1004	14844	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	95	6
3873MH0001840021401005C00	1005	14880	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	63	7
3873MH0001840021401006C00	1006	14916	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3873 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Vesini - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3873MH0001520011401010C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3873MH0002270001401031R00	1031	MOTOR COUNT:	14069	RANGE (cm):	6.4			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3873MH0002270001401032S00	1032	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3873	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3873			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3873MH0001520021401011C00	1011	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3873MH0001520021401012C00	1012	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3873MH0001520021401013C00	1013	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3873MH0001520021401014C00	1014	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3873MH0001520021401015C00	1015	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
3873MH0001520021401016C00	1016	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	95	6
3873MH0001520021401017C00	1017	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3873MH0001520021401018C00	1018	14213	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 07_July_2023

SOL 3873 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Vesini - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3873MH0001520011401020C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3873MH0002270001401029R00	1029	MOTOR COUNT:		14074	RANGE (cm):		6.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3873MH0002270001401030S00	1030	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jun-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3873		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3873
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3873MH0001520021401021C00	1021	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3873MH0001520021401022C00	1022	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3873MH0001520021401023C00	1023	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3873MH0001520021401024C00	1024	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3873MH0001520021401025C00	1025	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	127	5
3873MH0001520021401026C00	1026	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	95	6
3873MH0001520021401027C00	1027	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
3873MH0001520021401028C00	1028	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 06_July_2023

SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trapeza - before DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001680011401042C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3878MH0001710001401127R00	1127	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3878MH0001710001401128S00	1128	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3878	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0001680021401043C00	1043	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3877MH0001680021401044C00	1044	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3877MH0001680021401045C00	1045	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3877MH0001680021401046C00	1046	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3877MH0001680021401047C00	1047	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3877MH0001680021401048C00	1048	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3877MH0001680021401049C00	1049	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3877MH0001680021401050C00	1050	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_July_2023

SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trapeza - before DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001680011401052C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3877MH0001710001401125R00	1125	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3877MH0001710001401126S00	1126	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0001680021401053C00	1053	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3877MH0001680021401054C00	1054	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3877MH0001680021401055C00	1055	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3877MH0001680021401056C00	1056	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3877MH0001680021401057C00	1057	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3877MH0001680021401058C00	1058	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3877MH0001680021401059C00	1059	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3877MH0001680021401060C00	1060	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_July_2023

SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trapeza - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001680011401064C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3877MH0001710001401123R00	1123	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3877MH0001710001401124S00	1124	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0001680021401065C00	1065	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3877MH0001680021401066C00	1066	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3877MH0001680021401067C00	1067	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3877MH0001680021401068C00	1068	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3877MH0001680021401069C00	1069	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3877MH0001680021401070C00	1070	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3877MH0001680021401071C00	1071	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3877MH0001680021401072C00	1072	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trapeza - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001680011401074C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3877MH0001710001401121R00	1121	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3877MH0001710001401122S00	1122	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0001680021401075C00	1075	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3877MH0001680021401076C00	1076	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3877MH0001680021401077C00	1077	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3877MH0001680021401078C00	1078	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3877MH0001680021401079C00	1079	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3877MH0001680021401080C00	1080	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3877MH0001680021401081C00	1081	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3877MH0001680021401082C00	1082	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Trapeza - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0003020011401084C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3877MH0001710001401119R00	1119	MOTOR COUNT:		14688	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3877MH0001710001401120S00	1120	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0003020021401085C00	1085	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
3877MH0003020021401086C00	1086	14598	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	223	2
3877MH0003020021401087C00	1087	14628	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	191	3
3877MH0003020021401088C00	1088	14658	3.91	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
3877MH0003020021401089C00	1089	14688	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3877MH0003020021401090C00	1090	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
3877MH0003020021401091C00	1091	14748	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
3877MH0003020021401092C00	1092	14778	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 06_July_2023

SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Analipsi - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001820011401096C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3877MH0001710001401117R00	1117	MOTOR COUNT:		14367	RANGE (cm):	4.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3877MH0001710001401118S00	1118	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3877MH0001820021401097C00	1097	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	255	1
3877MH0001820021401098C00	1098	14295	5.24	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	223	2
3877MH0001820021401099C00	1099	14319	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	191	3
3877MH0001820021401100C00	1100	14343	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	159	4
3877MH0001820021401101C00	1101	14367	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	127	5
3877MH0001820021401102C00	1102	14391	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	95	6
3877MH0001820021401103C00	1103	14415	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	63	7
3877MH0001820021401104C00	1104	14439	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 06_July_2023

SOL 3877 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Analipsi - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3877MH0001820011401106C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3877MH0001710001401115R00		1115		MOTOR COUNT:		14361		RANGE (cm): 5.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3877MH0001710001401116S00		1116		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		3-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3877		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3877	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3877MH0001820021401107C00	1107	14265	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	255	1		
3877MH0001820021401108C00	1108	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	223	2		
3877MH0001820021401109C00	1109	14313	5.16	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	191	3		
3877MH0001820021401110C00	1110	14337	5.06	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	159	4		
3877MH0001820021401111C00	1111	14361	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	127	5		
3877MH0001820021401112C00	1112	14385	4.86	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	95	6		
3877MH0001820021401113C00	1113	14409	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	63	7		
3877MH0001820021401114C00	1114	14433	4.67	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8		

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Roghi - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0001820011401152C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3880MH0001630001401221R00	1221	MOTOR COUNT:		14045	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3880MH0001630001401222S00	1222	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3880MH0001820021401153C00	1153	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3880MH0001820021401154C00	1154	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3880MH0001820021401155C00	1155	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3880MH0001820021401156C00	1156	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3880MH0001820021401157C00	1157	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3880MH0001820021401158C00	1158	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
3880MH0001820021401159C00	1159	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3880MH0001820021401160C00	1160	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Roghi - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0001820011401162C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3880MH0001630001401219R00	1219	MOTOR COUNT:		14050	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3880MH0001630001401220S00	1220	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3880MH0001820021401163C00	1163	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
3880MH0001820021401164C00	1164	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
3880MH0001820021401165C00	1165	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3880MH0001820021401166C00	1166	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3880MH0001820021401167C00	1167	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3880MH0001820021401168C00	1168	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
3880MH0001820021401169C00	1169	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3880MH0001820021401170C00	1170	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Roghi - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0001840011401172C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3880MH0001630001401217R00		1217		MOTOR COUNT:		14790		RANGE (cm): 3.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3880MH0001630001401218S00		1218		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		6-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3880MH0001840021401173C00	1173	14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	255	1		
3880MH0001840021401174C00	1174	14682	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	223	2		
3880MH0001840021401175C00	1175	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	191	3		
3880MH0001840021401176C00	1176	14754	3.63	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	159	4		
3880MH0001840021401177C00	1177	14790	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	127	5		
3880MH0001840021401178C00	1178	14826	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	95	6		
3880MH0001840021401179C00	1179	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	63	7		
3880MH0001840021401180C00	1180	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Xerocambos - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~20 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0008540011401182C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3880MH0001630001401215R00		1215		MOTOR COUNT:		13103		RANGE (cm): 22.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3880MH0001630001401216S00		1216		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		6-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3880MH0008540021401183C00	1183	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	255	1		
3880MH0008540021401184C00	1184	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	223	2		
3880MH0008540021401185C00	1185	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	191	3		
3880MH0008540021401186C00	1186	13073	23.47	-1.4	1.6	89.5	5.2	159	4		
3880MH0008540021401187C00	1187	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	127	5		
3880MH0008540021401188C00	1188	13133	20.84	-1.1	1.2	80.3	4.1	95	6		
3880MH0008540021401189C00	1189	13163	19.71	-1.0	1.1	76.3	3.7	63	7		
3880MH0008540021401190C00	1190	13193	18.69	-0.9	1.0	72.7	3.3	31	8		

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Xerocambos - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~20 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0008540011401192C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3880MH0001630001401213R00		1213		MOTOR COUNT:		13112		RANGE (cm): 21.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3880MH0001630001401214S00		1214		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		6-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3880MH0008540021401193C00	1193	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	255	1		
3880MH0008540021401194C00	1194	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	223	2		
3880MH0008540021401195C00	1195	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	191	3		
3880MH0008540021401196C00	1196	13082	23.04	-1.4	1.5	88.0	5.0	159	4		
3880MH0008540021401197C00	1197	13112	21.70	-1.2	1.3	83.3	4.4	127	5		
3880MH0008540021401198C00	1198	13142	20.49	-1.1	1.2	79.0	4.0	95	6		
3880MH0008540021401199C00	1199	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	63	7		
3880MH0008540021401200C00	1200	13202	18.40	-0.9	0.9	71.7	3.2	31	8		

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SOL 3880 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Xerocambos - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~20 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3880MH0008540011401202C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3880MH0001630001401211R00		1211		MOTOR COUNT:		13106		RANGE (cm): 22.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3880MH0001630001401212S00		1212		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00854		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		6-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3880		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3880	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3880MH0008540021401203C00	1203	12986	28.54	-2.0	2.3	107.4	7.7	255	1		
3880MH0008540021401204C00	1204	13016	26.58	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	223	2		
3880MH0008540021401205C00	1205	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	191	3		
3880MH0008540021401206C00	1206	13076	23.33	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	159	4		
3880MH0008540021401207C00	1207	13106	21.96	-1.2	1.4	84.2	4.6	127	5		
3880MH0008540021401208C00	1208	13136	20.72	-1.1	1.2	79.8	4.1	95	6		
3880MH0008540021401209C00	1209	13166	19.60	-1.0	1.1	75.9	3.6	63	7		
3880MH0008540021401210C00	1210	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	31	8		

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SOL 3885 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Planitero - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3885MH0001680011401226C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3885MH0002650001401247R00	1247	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3885MH0002650001401248S00	1248	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3885	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3885	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3885MH0001680021401227C00	1227	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3885MH0001680021401228C00	1228	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3885MH0001680021401229C00	1229	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3885MH0001680021401230C00	1230	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3885MH0001680021401231C00	1231	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3885MH0001680021401232C00	1232	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3885MH0001680021401233C00	1233	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3885MH0001680021401234C00	1234	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_July_2023

SOL 3885 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Planitero - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3885MH0001680011401236C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3885MH0002650001401245R00	1245	MOTOR COUNT:		14040	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3885MH0002650001401246S00	1246	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	11-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3885	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3885	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3885MH0001680021401237C00	1237	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3885MH0001680021401238C00	1238	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3885MH0001680021401239C00	1239	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3885MH0001680021401240C00	1240	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3885MH0001680021401241C00	1241	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3885MH0001680021401242C00	1242	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3885MH0001680021401243C00	1243	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3885MH0001680021401244C00	1244	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 17_July_2023

SOL 3887 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sounion - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3887MH0001680011401252C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3887MH0001930001401285R00	1285	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3887MH0001930001401286S00	1286	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3887	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3887	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3887MH0001680021401253C00	1253	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
3887MH0001680021401254C00	1254	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3887MH0001680021401255C00	1255	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3887MH0001680021401256C00	1256	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3887MH0001680021401257C00	1257	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3887MH0001680021401258C00	1258	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3887MH0001680021401259C00	1259	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3887MH0001680021401260C00	1260	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 17_July_2023

SOL 3887 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sounion - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3887MH0001680011401262C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3887MH0001930001401283R00	1283	MOTOR COUNT:		14037	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3887MH0001930001401284S00	1284	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	13-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3887	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3887	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3887MH0001680021401263C00	1263	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3887MH0001680021401264C00	1264	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
3887MH0001680021401265C00	1265	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
3887MH0001680021401266C00	1266	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3887MH0001680021401267C00	1267	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
3887MH0001680021401268C00	1268	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3887MH0001680021401269C00	1269	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3887MH0001680021401270C00	1270	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3887 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sounion - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3887MH0007960011401272C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3887MH0001930001401281R00	1281	MOTOR COUNT:		14946	RANGE (cm):		3.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3887MH0001930001401282S00	1282	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3887	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3887	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3887MH0007960021401273C00	1273	14778	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	255	1
3887MH0007960021401274C00	1274	14820	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
3887MH0007960021401275C00	1275	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	191	3
3887MH0007960021401276C00	1276	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	159	4
3887MH0007960021401277C00	1277	14946	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	127	5
3887MH0007960021401278C00	1278	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	95	6
3887MH0007960021401279C00	1279	15030	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	63	7
3887MH0007960021401280C00	1280	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 17_July_2023

SOL 3889 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thermopylae - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3889MH0001820011401290C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3890MH0002270001401355R00	1355	MOTOR COUNT:		14026	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3890MH0002270001401356S00	1356	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3889	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3890	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3889MH0001820021401291C00	1291	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3889MH0001820021401292C00	1292	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3889MH0001820021401293C00	1293	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3889MH0001820021401294C00	1294	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3889MH0001820021401295C00	1295	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3889MH0001820021401296C00	1296	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3889MH0001820021401297C00	1297	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3889MH0001820021401298C00	1298	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3889 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thermopylae - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3889MH0001820011401300C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3890MH0002270001401353R00	1353	MOTOR COUNT:		14022	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3890MH0002270001401354S00	1354	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3889	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3890	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3889MH0001820021401301C00	1301	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3889MH0001820021401302C00	1302	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3889MH0001820021401303C00	1303	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3889MH0001820021401304C00	1304	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3889MH0001820021401305C00	1305	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3889MH0001820021401306C00	1306	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3889MH0001820021401307C00	1307	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3889MH0001820021401308C00	1308	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3889 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zachlorou - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3889MH0001820011401312C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3890MH0002270001401351R00	1351	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3890MH0002270001401352S00	1352	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3889	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3890	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3889MH0001820021401313C00	1313	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3889MH0001820021401314C00	1314	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3889MH0001820021401315C00	1315	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3889MH0001820021401316C00	1316	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3889MH0001820021401317C00	1317	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3889MH0001820021401318C00	1318	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3889MH0001820021401319C00	1319	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3889MH0001820021401320C00	1320	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3889 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zachlorou - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3889MH0001820011401322C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3890MH0002270001401349R00	1349	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3890MH0002270001401350S00	1350	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3889	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3890	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3889MH0001820021401323C00	1323	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3889MH0001820021401324C00	1324	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3889MH0001820021401325C00	1325	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3889MH0001820021401326C00	1326	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3889MH0001820021401327C00	1327	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3889MH0001820021401328C00	1328	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3889MH0001820021401329C00	1329	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3889MH0001820021401330C00	1330	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3889 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Zachlorou - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3889MH0004260011401338C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3890MH0002270001401347R00	1347	MOTOR COUNT:		15111	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3890MH0002270001401348S00	1348	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	16-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3889	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3890	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3889MH0004260021401339C00	1339	14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
3889MH0004260021401340C00	1340	14967	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
3889MH0004260021401341C00	1341	15015	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
3889MH0004260021401342C00	1342	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
3889MH0004260021401343C00	1343	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3889MH0004260021401344C00	1344	15159	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
3889MH0004260021401345C00	1345	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3889MH0004260021401346C00	1346	15255	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

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SOL 3892 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nasia - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3892MH0001730011401360C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3892MH0001930001401393R00	1393	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3892MH0001930001401394S00	1394	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3892	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3892	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3892MH0001730021401361C00	1361	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3892MH0001730021401362C00	1362	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3892MH0001730021401363C00	1363	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3892MH0001730021401364C00	1364	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3892MH0001730021401365C00	1365	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3892MH0001730021401366C00	1366	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3892MH0001730021401367C00	1367	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3892MH0001730021401368C00	1368	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3892 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nasia - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3892MH0001730011401370C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3892MH0001930001401391R00	1391	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3892MH0001930001401392S00	1392	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3892	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3892	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3892MH0001730021401371C00	1371	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3892MH0001730021401372C00	1372	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3892MH0001730021401373C00	1373	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3892MH0001730021401374C00	1374	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3892MH0001730021401375C00	1375	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3892MH0001730021401376C00	1376	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3892MH0001730021401377C00	1377	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3892MH0001730021401378C00	1378	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3892 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Nasia - ~1 cm standoff										
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3892MH0007960011401380C00						
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3892MH0001930001401389R00		1389		MOTOR COUNT:		15072		RANGE (cm): 2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3892MH0001930001401390S00		1390		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3892		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3892	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8			
				NEAR	FAR							
3892MH0007960021401381C00	1381	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1			
3892MH0007960021401382C00	1382	14946	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	223	2			
3892MH0007960021401383C00	1383	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3			
3892MH0007960021401384C00	1384	15030	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4			
3892MH0007960021401385C00	1385	15072	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5			
3892MH0007960021401386C00	1386	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6			
3892MH0007960021401387C00	1387	15156	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7			
3892MH0007960021401388C00	1388	15198	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8			

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SOL 3895 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3895MH0001680011401398C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3897MH0002270001401457R00	1457	MOTOR COUNT:		14223	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3897MH0002270001401458S00	1458	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3895	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3897	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3895MH0001680021401399C00	1399	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	255	1
3895MH0001680021401400C00	1400	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	223	2
3895MH0001680021401401C00	1401	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	191	3
3895MH0001680021401402C00	1402	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	159	4
3895MH0001680021401403C00	1403	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3895MH0001680021401404C00	1404	14241	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	95	6
3895MH0001680021401405C00	1405	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3895MH0001680021401406C00	1406	14277	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3895 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3895MH0001680011401408C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3897MH0002270001401455R00	1455	MOTOR COUNT:		14224	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3897MH0002270001401456S00	1456	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3895	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3897	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3895MH0001680021401409C00	1409	14152	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	255	1
3895MH0001680021401410C00	1410	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	223	2
3895MH0001680021401411C00	1411	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	191	3
3895MH0001680021401412C00	1412	14206	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	159	4
3895MH0001680021401413C00	1413	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3895MH0001680021401414C00	1414	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	95	6
3895MH0001680021401415C00	1415	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3895MH0001680021401416C00	1416	14278	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3895 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Trinite - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3895MH0001680011401420C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3897MH0002270001401453R00		1453		MOTOR COUNT:		14037		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3897MH0002270001401454S00		1454		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3895		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3897	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3895MH0001680021401421C00	1421	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1		
3895MH0001680021401422C00	1422	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2		
3895MH0001680021401423C00	1423	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3		
3895MH0001680021401424C00	1424	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4		
3895MH0001680021401425C00	1425	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5		
3895MH0001680021401426C00	1426	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6		
3895MH0001680021401427C00	1427	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3895MH0001680021401428C00	1428	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8		

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SOL 3895 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Trinite - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3895MH0001680011401430C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3897MH0002270001401451R00		1451		MOTOR COUNT:		14040		RANGE (cm): 6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3897MH0002270001401452S00		1452		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		22-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3895		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3897	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3895MH0001680021401431C00	1431	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1		
3895MH0001680021401432C00	1432	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2		
3895MH0001680021401433C00	1433	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3		
3895MH0001680021401434C00	1434	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4		
3895MH0001680021401435C00	1435	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5		
3895MH0001680021401436C00	1436	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6		
3895MH0001680021401437C00	1437	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7		
3895MH0001680021401438C00	1438	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 24_July_2023

SOL 3895 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target La_Trinite – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3895MH0007430011401440C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3897MH0002270001401449R00	1449	MOTOR COUNT:		15198	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3897MH0002270001401450S00	1450	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3895	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3897	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3895MH0007430021401441C00	1441	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	255	1
3895MH0007430021401442C00	1442	15090	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	223	2
3895MH0007430021401443C00	1443	15126	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
3895MH0007430021401444C00	1444	15162	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
3895MH0007430021401445C00	1445	15198	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
3895MH0007430021401446C00	1446	15234	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
3895MH0007430021401447C00	1447	15270	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
3895MH0007430021401448C00	1448	15306	2.47	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2023

SOL 3898 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mamore - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3898MH0001820011401464C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3898MH0001930001401497R00	1497	MOTOR COUNT:	14018	RANGE (cm):	6.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3898MH0001930001401498S00	1498	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3898	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3898			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3898MH0001820021401465C00	1465	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3898MH0001820021401466C00	1466	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3898MH0001820021401467C00	1467	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3898MH0001820021401468C00	1468	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3898MH0001820021401469C00	1469	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3898MH0001820021401470C00	1470	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
3898MH0001820021401471C00	1471	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3898MH0001820021401472C00	1472	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2023

SOL 3898 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mamore - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3898MH0001820011401474C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3898MH0001930001401495R00	1495	MOTOR COUNT:	14022	RANGE (cm):	6.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3898MH0001930001401496S00	1496	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3898	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3898			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3898MH0001820021401475C00	1475	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3898MH0001820021401476C00	1476	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3898MH0001820021401477C00	1477	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3898MH0001820021401478C00	1478	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3898MH0001820021401479C00	1479	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3898MH0001820021401480C00	1480	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3898MH0001820021401481C00	1481	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3898MH0001820021401482C00	1482	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 01_August_2023

SOL 3898 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mamore – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3898MH0001840011401484C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3898MH0001930001401493R00	1493	MOTOR COUNT:		14736	RANGE (cm):		3.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3898MH0001930001401494S00	1494	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00184	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3898	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3898	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3898MH0001840021401485C00	1485	14592	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
3898MH0001840021401486C00	1486	14628	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2
3898MH0001840021401487C00	1487	14664	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
3898MH0001840021401488C00	1488	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
3898MH0001840021401489C00	1489	14736	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
3898MH0001840021401490C00	1490	14772	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	95	6
3898MH0001840021401491C00	1491	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	63	7
3898MH0001840021401492C00	1492	14844	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3899 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guainia - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3899MH0002990011401502C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3899MH0002270001401561R00	1561	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3899MH0002270001401562S00	1562	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3899	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3899	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3899MH0002990021401503C00	1503	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
3899MH0002990021401504C00	1504	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3899MH0002990021401505C00	1505	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3899MH0002990021401506C00	1506	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3899MH0002990021401507C00	1507	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3899MH0002990021401508C00	1508	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3899MH0002990021401509C00	1509	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3899MH0002990021401510C00	1510	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3899 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guainia - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3899MH0002990011401512C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3899MH0002270001401559R00	1559	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3899MH0002270001401560S00	1560	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3899	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3899	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3899MH0002990021401513C00	1513	13858	7.88	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3899MH0002990021401514C00	1514	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3899MH0002990021401515C00	1515	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3899MH0002990021401516C00	1516	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3899MH0002990021401517C00	1517	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3899MH0002990021401518C00	1518	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3899MH0002990021401519C00	1519	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3899MH0002990021401520C00	1520	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3899 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Guainia - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3899MH0003350011401522C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3899MH0002270001401557R00	1557	MOTOR COUNT:		14706	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3899MH0002270001401558S00	1558	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00335	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3899	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3899	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3899MH0003350021401523C00	1523	14490	4.46	-0.1	0.1	22.6	0.3	255	1
3899MH0003350021401524C00	1524	14544	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	223	2
3899MH0003350021401525C00	1525	14598	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	191	3
3899MH0003350021401526C00	1526	14652	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
3899MH0003350021401527C00	1527	14706	3.77	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	127	5
3899MH0003350021401528C00	1528	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	95	6
3899MH0003350021401529C00	1529	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	63	7
3899MH0003350021401530C00	1530	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3899 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mocambo - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3899MH0003080011401534C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3899MH0002270001401555R00	1555	MOTOR COUNT:		14166	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3899MH0002270001401556S00	1556	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3899	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3899	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3899MH0003080021401535C00	1535	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3899MH0003080021401536C00	1536	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3899MH0003080021401537C00	1537	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3899MH0003080021401538C00	1538	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	159	4
3899MH0003080021401539C00	1539	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
3899MH0003080021401540C00	1540	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
3899MH0003080021401541C00	1541	14298	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	63	7
3899MH0003080021401542C00	1542	14364	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3899 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mocambo – stereo-2 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3899MH0003080011401544C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3899MH0002270001401553R00	1553	MOTOR COUNT:		14180	RANGE (cm):		5.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3899MH0002270001401554S00	1554	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Jul-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3899		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3899
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3899MH0003080021401545C00	1545	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3899MH0003080021401546C00	1546	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
3899MH0003080021401547C00	1547	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
3899MH0003080021401548C00	1548	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
3899MH0003080021401549C00	1549	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
3899MH0003080021401550C00	1550	14246	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	95	6
3899MH0003080021401551C00	1551	14312	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
3899MH0003080021401552C00	1552	14378	4.89	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3900 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Porta_Walter - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3900MH0001680011401566C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3901MH0002270001401625R00	1625	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3901MH0002270001401626S00	1626	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3900	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3901	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3900MH0001680021401567C00	1567	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3900MH0001680021401568C00	1568	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3900MH0001680021401569C00	1569	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3900MH0001680021401570C00	1570	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3900MH0001680021401571C00	1571	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3900MH0001680021401572C00	1572	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3900MH0001680021401573C00	1573	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3900MH0001680021401574C00	1574	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3900 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Porta_Walter - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3900MH0001680011401576C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3901MH0002270001401623R00	1623	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3901MH0002270001401624S00	1624	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3900	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3901	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3900MH0001680021401577C00	1577	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3900MH0001680021401578C00	1578	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3900MH0001680021401579C00	1579	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3900MH0001680021401580C00	1580	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3900MH0001680021401581C00	1581	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3900MH0001680021401582C00	1582	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3900MH0001680021401583C00	1583	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3900MH0001680021401584C00	1584	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3900 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Porta_Walter - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3900MH0007430011401586C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3901MH0002270001401621R00	1621	MOTOR COUNT:	15160	RANGE (cm):	2.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3901MH0002270001401622S00	1622	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3900	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3901			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3900MH0007430021401587C00	1587	15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
3900MH0007430021401588C00	1588	15052	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
3900MH0007430021401589C00	1589	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
3900MH0007430021401590C00	1590	15124	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
3900MH0007430021401591C00	1591	15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
3900MH0007430021401592C00	1592	15196	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
3900MH0007430021401593C00	1593	15232	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3900MH0007430021401594C00	1594	15268	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3900 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Purace - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3900MH0001680011401598C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3901MH0002270001401619R00	1619	MOTOR COUNT:	14020	RANGE (cm):	6.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3901MH0002270001401620S00	1620	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3900	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3901			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3900MH0001680021401599C00	1599	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3900MH0001680021401600C00	1600	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3900MH0001680021401601C00	1601	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3900MH0001680021401602C00	1602	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3900MH0001680021401603C00	1603	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3900MH0001680021401604C00	1604	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3900MH0001680021401605C00	1605	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3900MH0001680021401606C00	1606	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3900 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Purace - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3900MH0001680011401608C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3901MH0002270001401617R00		1617		MOTOR COUNT:		14025		RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3901MH0002270001401618S00		1618		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		27-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3900		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3901	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3900MH0001680021401609C00	1609	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1		
3900MH0001680021401610C00	1610	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2		
3900MH0001680021401611C00	1611	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3		
3900MH0001680021401612C00	1612	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4		
3900MH0001680021401613C00	1613	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5		
3900MH0001680021401614C00	1614	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6		
3900MH0001680021401615C00	1615	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7		
3900MH0001680021401616C00	1616	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3902 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jamari - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3902MH0001680011401630C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3904MH0001930001401663R00	1663	MOTOR COUNT:		14016	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3904MH0001930001401664S00	1664	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3902	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3904		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3902MH0001680021401631C00	1631	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3902MH0001680021401632C00	1632	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3902MH0001680021401633C00	1633	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3902MH0001680021401634C00	1634	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3902MH0001680021401635C00	1635	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3902MH0001680021401636C00	1636	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3902MH0001680021401637C00	1637	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3902MH0001680021401638C00	1638	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3902 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jamari - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3902MH0001680011401640C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3904MH0001930001401661R00	1661	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3904MH0001930001401662S00	1662	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3902	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3904		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3902MH0001680021401641C00	1641	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3902MH0001680021401642C00	1642	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3902MH0001680021401643C00	1643	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3902MH0001680021401644C00	1644	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3902MH0001680021401645C00	1645	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3902MH0001680021401646C00	1646	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3902MH0001680021401647C00	1647	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3902MH0001680021401648C00	1648	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3902 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jamari – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3902MH0007430011401650C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3904MH0001930001401659R00	1659	MOTOR COUNT:		15119	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3904MH0001930001401660S00	1660	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3902	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3904	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3902MH0007430021401651C00	1651	14975	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3902MH0007430021401652C00	1652	15011	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3902MH0007430021401653C00	1653	15047	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3902MH0007430021401654C00	1654	15083	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3902MH0007430021401655C00	1655	15119	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3902MH0007430021401656C00	1656	15155	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
3902MH0007430021401657C00	1657	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3902MH0007430021401658C00	1658	15227	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3779–3902. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3780, 3781, 3796, 3798, 3799, 3800, 3801, 3803, 3807, 3808, 3810, 3812, 3817, 3818, 3819, 3821, 3823, 3834, 3835, 3837, 3838, 3839, 3845, 3846, 3851, 3853, 3855, 3858, 3859, 3860, 3862, 3864, 3866, 3867, 3871, 3873, 3877, 3878, 3880, 3885, 3887, 3889, 3890, 3892, 3895, 3897, 3898, 3899, 3900, 3901, 3902.**

updated: 03_April_2023

Sol 3780 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Mar-23
camera position	12
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI images of the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the targets Capanapro and Amanauo.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	3780MH0037100113045260C0	4526	autoFocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		3780MH0037100113045270C0	4527	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	3780MH0037200113045280C0	4528	autoFocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		3780MH0037200113045290C0	4529	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mNI00374	MAHLI cal target + wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	3780MH0037400113045300C0	4530	autoFocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3780MH0037400113045310C0	4531	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3780MH0037400113045320C0	4532	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mNI00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	3780MH0037300113045330C0	4533	autoFocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0037300113045340C0	4534	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00190	Capanapro ~25 cm standoff	3780MH0019000113045350C0	4535	autoFocus sub-frame for target Capanapro - standoff near 25 cm
		3780MH001900113045360C0	4536	target Capanapro - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00299	Capanapro stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3780MH0029900113045370C0	4537	autoFocus sub-frame for target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0029902113045380C0	4538	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0029903113045390C0	4539	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029904113045400C0	4540	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029905113045410C0	4541	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029906113045420C0	4542	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029907113045430C0	4543	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029908113045440C0	4544	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029909113045450C0	4545	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029910113045460C0	4546	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00299	Capanapro stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3780MH0029900113045470C0	4547	autoFocus sub-frame for target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH002990113045480C0	4548	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0029902113045490C0	4549	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029903113045500C0	4550	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029904113045510C0	4551	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029905113045520C0	4552	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029906113045530C0	4553	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029907113045540C0	4554	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029908113045550C0	4555	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029909113045560C0	4556	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00174	Capanapro ~2 cm standoff	3780MH0017400113045570C0	4557	autoFocus sub-frame for target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm
		3780MH001740113045580C0	4558	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm
		3780MH0017402113045590C0	4559	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017403113045600C0	4560	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017404113045610C0	4561	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017405113045620C0	4562	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017406113045630C0	4563	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017407113045640C0	4564	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017408113045650C0	4565	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0017409113045660C0	4566	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00190	Amanauo ~25 cm standoff	3780MH0019000113045670C0	4567	autoFocus sub-frame for target Amanauo - standoff near 25 cm
		3780MH001900113045680C0	4568	target Amanauo - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00299	Amanauo stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3780MH0029900113045690C0	4569	autoFocus sub-frame for target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH002990113045700C0	4570	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0029902113045710C0	4571	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029903113045720C0	4572	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029904113045730C0	4573	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029905113045740C0	4574	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029906113045750C0	4575	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029907113045760C0	4576	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029908113045770C0	4577	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029909113045780C0	4578	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00299	Amanauo stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3780MH0029900113045790C0	4579	autoFocus sub-frame for target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH002990113045800C0	4580	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3780MH0029902113045810C0	4581	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029903113045820C0	4582	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029904113045830C0	4583	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029905113045840C0	4584	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029906113045850C0	4585	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029907113045860C0	4586	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029908113045870C0	4587	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH0029909113045880C0	4588	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00796	Amanauo 1 cm standoff	3780MH00796001304589C00	4589	autofocus sub-frame for target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm
		3780MH00796001304590C00	4590	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm
		3780MH00796001304591C00	4591	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304592C00	4592	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304593C00	4593	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304594C00	4594	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304595C00	4595	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304596C00	4596	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304597C00	4597	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3780MH00796001304598C00	4598	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 27_March_2023

Sol 3781 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Mar-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3780 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	3781MH000163000130439900	4599	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4591-4598 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130460050	4600	target Amanauo - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4591-4598 - range map product
		3781MH000163000130460100	4601	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4581-4588 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130460250	4602	target Amanauo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4581-4588 - range map product
		3781MH000163000130460300	4603	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4571-4578 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130460450	4604	target Amanauo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4571-4578 - range map product
		3781MH000163000130460500	4605	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4559-4566 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130460650	4606	target Capanapro - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4559-4566 - range map product
		3781MH000163000130460700	4607	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4549-4556 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130460850	4608	target Capanapro - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4549-4556 - range map product
		3781MH000163000130460900	4609	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4539-4546 - best focus image product
		3781MH000163000130461050	4610	target Capanapro - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3780 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4539-4546 - range map product

updated: 14_April_2023

Sol 3796 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the DRT (brushed target Tarilandia and the focus stack images were merged.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the DRT (brushed target Tarilandia and the focus stack images were merged.		
acquired/performed date(s)		11-Apr-23		
camera position		4		Image ID:
total parent images		33		black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed		3		CPDPID:
total focus merge products		6		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products		39		
mN00190	Tarilandia after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3796MH001900011304611200	4611	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3796MH001900011304612000	4612	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Tarilandia after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3796MH001820011304613000	4613	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3796MH001820011304614000	4614	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3796MH001820011304615000	4615	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304616000	4616	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304617000	4617	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304618000	4618	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304619000	4619	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304620000	4620	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304621000	4621	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304622000	4622	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Tarilandia after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3796MH001820011304623000	4623	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3796MH001820011304624000	4624	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3796MH001820011304625000	4625	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304626000	4626	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304627000	4627	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304628000	4628	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304629000	4629	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304630000	4630	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304631000	4631	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001820011304632000	4632	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Tarilandia after DRT ~15 mm standoff	3796MH001840011304633000	4633	autoFocus sub-frame for target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3796MH001840011304634000	4634	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3796MH001840011304635000	4635	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304636000	4636	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304637000	4637	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304638000	4638	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304639000	4639	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304640000	4640	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304641000	4641	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3796MH001840011304642000	4642	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3796MH001930011304643000	4643	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4633-4642 - best focus image product
		3796MH001930011304644000	4644	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4635-4642 - range map product
		3796MH001930011304645000	4645	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4623-4632 - best focus image product
		3796MH001930011304646000	4646	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4625-4632 - range map product
		3796MH001930011304647000	4647	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4613-4622 - best focus image product
		3796MH001930011304648000	4648	target Tarilandia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3796 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4615-4622 - range map product

updated: 14_April_2023

Sol 3799 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16_Apr_23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3798 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	3799MH0053600090474900	4745	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4737-4744 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904746500	4746	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4737-4744 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904747000	4747	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-0 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4726-4733 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904748500	4748	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4726-4733 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904749000	4749	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4715-4722 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904750500	4750	target Duplki - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4715-4722 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904751000	4751	target Cantario - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4701-4708 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904752500	4752	target Cantario - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4701-4708 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904753000	4753	target Cantario - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4691-4698 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904754500	4754	target Cantario - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4691-4698 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904755000	4755	target Cantario - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4681-4688 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904756500	4756	target Cantario - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4681-4688 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904757000	4757	target Cantario - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4671-4678 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904758500	4758	target Cantario - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4671-4678 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904759000	4759	target Cantario - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4661-4668 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904760500	4760	target Cantario - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4661-4668 - range map product
		3799MH00536000904761000	4761	target Cantario - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4651-4658 - best focus image product
		3799MH00536000904762500	4762	target Cantario - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3798 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4651-4658 - range map product

Sol 3800 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	15-Apr-23	
		camera position	85	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	85	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the target Terra_Firme and the CRT-brushed target Lorenzo. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00290	Terra_Firme ~24 cm standoff	3800MH0019000208476300	4763	autofocus sub-frame for target Terra_Firme - standoff near 24 cm
		3800MH00190001080476400	4764	target Terra_Firme - standoff near 24 cm
mNI00459	Terra_Firme stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3800MH0045900208476500	4765	autofocus sub-frame for target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3800MH00459001080476600	4766	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3800MH0045900208476700	4767	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208476800	4768	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208476900	4769	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477000	4770	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477100	4771	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477200	4772	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477300	4773	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477400	4774	target Terra_Firme - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00459	Terra_Firme stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3800MH0045900208477500	4775	autofocus sub-frame for target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3800MH00459001080477600	4776	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3800MH0045900208477700	4777	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477800	4778	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208477900	4779	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208478000	4780	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208478100	4781	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208478200	4782	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208478300	4783	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0045900208478400	4784	target Terra_Firme - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00705	Lorenzo after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3800MH0070500208478500	4785	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3800MH00705001080478600	4786	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3800MH0070500208478700	4787	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00763	Lorenzo after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0076300208478800	4788	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH00763001080478900	4789	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH0076300208479000	4790	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3800MH0076300208479100	4791	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479200	4792	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479300	4793	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479400	4794	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479500	4795	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479600	4796	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479700	4797	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00763	Lorenzo after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0076300208479800	4798	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208479900	4799	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH0076300108048000	4800	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH0076300208480100	4801	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3800MH0076300208480200	4802	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208480300	4803	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208480400	4804	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208480500	4805	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208480600	4806	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0076300208480700	4807	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00705	Lorenzo after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0070500208480800	4808	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH00705001080480900	4809	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00705	Lorenzo after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0070500208481000	4810	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH00705001080481100	4811	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00705	Lorenzo after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0070500208481200	4812	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH00705001080481300	4813	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00705	Lorenzo after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH0070500208481400	4814	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH00705001080481500	4815	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00794	Lorenzo after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3800MH0079400208481600	4816	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3800MH00794001080481700	4817	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3800MH0079400208481800	4818	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3800MH0079400208481900	4819	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482000	4820	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482100	4821	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482200	4822	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482300	4823	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482400	4824	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH0079400208482500	4825	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3800MH0079400208482600	4826	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mNH00763	Lorenzo after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3800MH00763000894827C00	4827	autofocus sub-frame for target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH007630010804828C00	4828	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3800MH007630020804829C00	4829	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3800MH007630030704830C00	4830	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704831C00	4831	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704832C00	4832	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704833C00	4833	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704834C00	4834	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704835C00	4835	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3800MH007630030704836C00	4836	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3800MH007630030704837C00	4837	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNH00312	MAH4 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin elec mesh, inlet cover open, position 1 of 3, imaging at right	3800MH00312000704838C00	4838	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		3800MH003120010704839C00	4839	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mNH00316	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3800MH00316000704840C00	4840	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mNH00316	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3800MH00316000704841C00	4841	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mNH00228	~19 cm above open CheMin inlet	3800MH00228000704842C00	4842	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 17_April_2023

Sol 3801 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Apr-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	13
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3800 were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3460 (data from Sol 3562-3724) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3801MH00163000704843R00	4843	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4830-4837 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000704844S00	4844	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4830-4837 - range map product
		3801MH00163000704845R00	4845	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4819-4826 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000704846S00	4846	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4819-4826 - range map product
		3801MH00163000704847R00	4847	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4802-4809 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000704848S00	4848	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4802-4809 - range map product
		3801MH00163000704849R00	4849	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4791-4798 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000604850S00	4850	target Lorenzo - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4791-4798 - range map product
		3801MH00163000604851R00	4851	target Terra_Firma - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4777-4784 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000604852S00	4852	target Terra_Firma - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4777-4784 - range map product
		3801MH00163000604853R00	4853	target Terra_Firma - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4767-4774 - best focus image product
		3801MH00163000604854S00	4854	target Terra_Firma - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3800 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4767-4774 - range map product

updated: 24_April_2023

Sol 3803 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Apr-23
camera position	6
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	32

MAHLI imaged the ChemCam RWEE window and internal hardware. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mHN0052	ChemCam RWEE diagnostic imaging MAHLI at 45° angle to ChemCam -25 cm standoff	3803MH00520001100001C00	1	autoFocus sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm
		3803MH00520001140002C00	2	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm
		3803MH00520001140003C00	3	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140004C00	4	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140005C00	5	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140006C00	6	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140007C00	7	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140008C00	8	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140009C00	9	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140010C00	10	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140011C00	11	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 9 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140012C00	12	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 10 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140013C00	13	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 11 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140014C00	14	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 12 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140015C00	15	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 13 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140016C00	16	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 14 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140017C00	17	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 15 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140018C00	18	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 16 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140019C00	19	auto-exposure sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm
		3803MH00520001140020C00	20	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - using exposure determined by preceding sub-frame - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm
		3803MH00520001140021C00	21	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140022C00	22	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140023C00	23	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140024C00	24	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3803MH00520001140025C00	25	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3803MH00520001140026C00	26	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3803MH00520001140027C00	27	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3803MH00520001140028C00	28	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mHN00768	Focus Merges	3803MH0076800140029W00	29	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3803 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 21-28 - best focus image product
		3803MH0076800140030S00	30	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3803 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 21-28 - range map product
		3803MH0076800140031R00	31	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3803 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 9-12 - best focus image product
		3803MH0076800140032S00	32	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEE) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3803 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 9-12 - range map product

updated: 24_April_2023

Sol 3807 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Apr-23
camera position	2
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Floresta and the target Calama.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Floresta after DRT ~25 cm standoff	33	33	autofocus sub-frame for target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		34	34	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Floresta after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	35	35	autofocus sub-frame for target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		36	36	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		37	37	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		38	38	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		39	39	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		40	40	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		41	41	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		42	42	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		43	43	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		44	44	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Floresta after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	45	45	autofocus sub-frame for target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		46	46	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		47	47	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		48	48	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		49	49	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		50	50	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		51	51	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		52	52	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		53	53	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		54	54	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00337	Floresta after DRT stereo-2 ~2 cm standoff	55	55	autofocus sub-frame for target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		56	56	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		57	57	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		58	58	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		59	59	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		60	60	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		61	61	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		62	62	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		63	63	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		64	64	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Calama ~25 cm standoff	65	65	autofocus sub-frame for target Calama - standoff near 25 cm
		66	66	target Calama - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Calama stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	67	67	autofocus sub-frame for target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		68	68	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		69	69	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		70	70	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		71	71	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		72	72	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		73	73	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		74	74	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		75	75	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		76	76	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Calama stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	77	77	autofocus sub-frame for target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		78	78	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		79	79	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		80	80	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		81	81	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		82	82	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		83	83	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		84	84	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		85	85	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		86	86	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 24_April_2023

Sol 3808 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Apr-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3807 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3808MH0002270001400087900	87	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 79-86 - best focus image product
		3808MH0002270001400088500	88	target Calama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 79-86 - range map product
		3808MH0002270001400089000	89	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 69-76 - best focus image product
		3808MH0002270001400090500	90	target Calama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 69-76 - range map product
		3808MH0002270001400091000	91	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - best focus image product
		3808MH0002270001400092500	92	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 57-64 - range map product
		3808MH0002270001400093000	93	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 47-54 - best focus image product
		3808MH0002270001400094500	94	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 47-54 - range map product
		3808MH0002270001400095000	95	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 37-44 - best focus image product
		3808MH0002270001400096500	96	target Floresta - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3807 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 37-44 - range map product

updated: 27_April_2023

Sol 3810 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	04-Apr-2023-04pm	
		camera position:	4	image ID:
		total parent images:	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Anortosis_Repartimento and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Anortosis_Repartimento after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3810MH00190001400979Z00	97	autoFocus sub-frame for target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3810MH00190001400980Z00	98	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN002168	Anortosis_Repartimento after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3810MH00168001400999Z00	99	autoFocus sub-frame for target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3810MH00168001400100Z00	100	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3810MH00168001400101Z00	101	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400102Z00	102	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400103Z00	103	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400104Z00	104	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400105Z00	105	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400106Z00	106	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400107Z00	107	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400108Z00	108	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Anortosis_Repartimento after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3810MH00168001400109Z00	109	autoFocus sub-frame for target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3810MH00168001400110Z00	110	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3810MH00168001400111Z00	111	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400112Z00	112	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400113Z00	113	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400114Z00	114	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400115Z00	115	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400116Z00	116	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400117Z00	117	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00168001400118Z00	118	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002796	Anortosis_Repartimento after DRT ~5 mm standoff	3810MH00796001400119Z00	119	autoFocus sub-frame for target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3810MH00796001400120Z00	120	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3810MH00796001400121Z00	121	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400122Z00	122	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400123Z00	123	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400124Z00	124	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400125Z00	125	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400126Z00	126	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400127Z00	127	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3810MH00796001400128Z00	128	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	3810MH00193001400129Z00	129	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 121-128 - best focus image product
		3810MH00193001400130Z00	130	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 121-128 - range map product
		3810MH00193001400131Z00	131	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 111-118 - best focus image product
		3810MH00193001400132Z00	132	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 111-118 - range map product
		3810MH00193001400133Z00	133	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 101-108 - best focus image product
3810MH00193001400134Z00	134	target Anortosis_Repartimento - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3810 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 101-108 - range map product		

updated: 01_May_2023

Sol 3812 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	01-Apr-2023
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Armero and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPVID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Armero after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3812MH0019000140013500	135	autoFocus sub-frame for target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3812MH0019000140013600	136	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Armero after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3812MH0017300140013700	137	autoFocus sub-frame for target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3812MH0017300140013800	138	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3812MH0017300140013900	139	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014000	140	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014100	141	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014200	142	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014300	143	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014400	144	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014500	145	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140014600	146	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Armero after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3812MH0017300140014700	147	autoFocus sub-frame for target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3812MH0017300140014800	148	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3812MH0017300140014900	149	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015000	150	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015100	151	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015200	152	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015300	153	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015400	154	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015500	155	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0017300140015600	156	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Armero after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3812MH0030200140015700	157	autoFocus sub-frame for target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3812MH0030200140015800	158	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3812MH0030200140015900	159	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016000	160	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016100	161	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016200	162	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016300	163	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016400	164	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016500	165	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3812MH0030200140016600	166	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3812MH0019300140016700	167	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 159-166 - best focus image product
		3812MH0019300140016800	168	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 159-166 - range map product
		3812MH0019300140016900	169	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 149-156 - best focus image product
		3812MH0019300140017000	170	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 149-156 - range map product
		3812MH0019300140017100	171	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 139-146 - best focus image product
3812MH0019300140017200	172	target Armero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3812 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 139-146 - range map product		

updated: 05_May_2023

Sol 3817 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	3-May-23	
		camera positions	6	Image ID:
		total parent images:	35	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	35	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Ubajara before and after an attempted drill bit preload test.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Ubajara before DRT stereo-1 ~25 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400179200	173	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3817MH000170001400179400	174	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00187	Ubajara before DRT stereo-2 ~24 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400179500	175	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
		3817MH000170001400179600	176	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00173	Ubajara before DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400179700	177	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400179800	178	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400179900	179	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400180000	180	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400181000	181	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400182000	182	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400183000	183	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400184000	184	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Ubajara before DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400185000	185	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400186000	186	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400187000	187	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400188000	188	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400189000	189	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400190000	190	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400191000	191	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400192000	192	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Ubajara before DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400193000	193	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400194000	194	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400195000	195	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400196000	196	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400197000	197	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400198000	198	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3817MH000170001400199000	199	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400200000	200	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Ubajara before DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3817MH000170001400201000	201	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400202000	202	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400203000	203	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400204000	204	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400205000	205	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3817MH000170001400206000	206	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Ubajara before DRT after drill bit preload attempt ~34 cm standoff	3817MH0004650001400207000	207	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - attempted drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload attempt - before sol 3819 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 34 cm
		3817MH0004650001400208000	208	intended Ubajara drill site - attempted drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload attempt - before sol 3819 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 34 cm

updated: 03_May_2023

Sol 3818 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	3 May 23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3817 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00289	Focus Merges	3818MH00193000140020900	209	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 199-206 - best focus image product
		3818MH001930001400210500	210	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 199-206 - range map product
		3818MH001930001400211900	211	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 189-196 - best focus image product
		3818MH001930001400212500	212	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 189-196 - range map product
		3818MH001930001400213900	213	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 179-186 - best focus image product
		3818MH001930001400214500	214	intended Ubajara drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3817 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 179-186 - range map product

updated: 27_October_2023

Sol 3819 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-May-23
camera position	6
total parent images	43
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	50

MAHLI images of intended drill target Ubajara after DRT. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Ubajara after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3819MH0019000140021500	215	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3819MH0019000140021600	216	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Ubajara after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3819MH0018200140021700	217	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140021800	218	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140021900	219	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022000	220	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022100	221	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022200	222	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022300	223	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022400	224	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022500	225	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140022600	226	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Ubajara after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3819MH0018200140022700	227	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140022800	228	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140022900	229	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023000	230	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023100	231	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023200	232	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023300	233	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023400	234	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023500	235	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140023600	236	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00426	Ubajara after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3819MH0042600140023700	237	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3819MH0042600140023800	238	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3819MH0042600140023900	239	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024000	240	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024100	241	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024200	242	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024300	243	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024400	244	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024500	245	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0042600140024600	246	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Ubajara after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3819MH0018200140024700	247	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140024800	248	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3819MH0018200140024900	249	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025000	250	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025100	251	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025200	252	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025300	253	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025400	254	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025500	255	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3819MH0018200140025600	256	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00183	Focus Merges	3819MH0018300140025700	257	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 249-256 - best focus image product
		3819MH0018300140025800	258	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 249-256 - range map product
		3819MH0018300140025900	259	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 239-246 - best focus image product
		3819MH0018300140026000	260	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 239-246 - range map product
		3819MH0018300140026100	261	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 229-236 - best focus image product
		3819MH0018300140026200	262	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 229-236 - range map product
		3819MH0018300140026300	263	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 219-226 - best focus image product
		3819MH0018300140026400	264	intended Ubajara drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3819 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 219-226 - range map product

updated: 27_October_2023

Sol 3821 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	7-May-23	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	55	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	60	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Ubajara after a 4-8 bit pre-load test. MAHLI also imaged the targets Itha_Grande and Bwesse_Kiki. The focus stack images were merged as well.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00465	Ubajara after DRT after drill bit pre-load attempt ~35 cm standoff	3821MH000465001400265000	265	autofocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill site - drill bit pre-load test - image acquired after pre-load test - after sol 3819 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3821MH000465001400266000	266	intended Ubajara drill site - drill bit pre-load test - image acquired after pre-load test - after sol 3819 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN00190	Itha_Grande ~24 cm standoff	3821MH000190001400267000	267	autofocus sub-frame for target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		3821MH000190001400268000	268	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00152	Itha_Grande APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3821MH000152001400269000	269	autofocus sub-frame for target Itha_Grande - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400270000	270	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400271000	271	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400272000	272	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400273000	273	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400274000	274	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400275000	275	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400276000	276	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400277000	277	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400278000	278	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Itha_Grande APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3821MH000152001400279000	279	autofocus sub-frame for target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400280000	280	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400281000	281	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400282000	282	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400283000	283	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400284000	284	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400285000	285	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400286000	286	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400287000	287	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400288000	288	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Itha_Grande APXS spot 1 ~45 mm standoff	3821MH000152001400289000	289	autofocus sub-frame for target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400290000	290	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3821MH000152001400291000	291	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400292000	292	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400293000	293	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400294000	294	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400295000	295	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400296000	296	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400297000	297	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000152001400298000	298	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Bwesse_Kiki ~23 cm standoff	3821MH000190001400299000	299	autofocus sub-frame for target Bwesse_Kiki - standoff near 23 cm
		3821MH000190001400300000	300	target Bwesse_Kiki - standoff near 23 cm
mN00299	Bwesse_Kiki stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3821MH000299001400301000	301	autofocus sub-frame for target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3821MH000299001400302000	302	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3821MH000299001400303000	303	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400304000	304	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400305000	305	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400306000	306	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400307000	307	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400308000	308	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400309000	309	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400310000	310	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Bwesse_Kiki stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3821MH000299001400311000	311	autofocus sub-frame for target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3821MH000299001400312000	312	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3821MH000299001400313000	313	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400314000	314	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400315000	315	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400316000	316	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400317000	317	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400318000	318	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400319000	319	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3821MH000299001400320000	320	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3821MH0002270001400321000	321	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 313-320 - best focus image product
		3821MH0002270001400322000	322	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 313-320 - range map product
		3821MH0002270001400323000	323	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 303-310 - best focus image product
		3821MH0002270001400324000	324	target Bwesse_Kiki - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 303-310 - range map product
		3821MH0002270001400325000	325	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 291-298 - best focus image product
		3821MH0002270001400326000	326	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 291-298 - range map product
		3821MH0002270001400327000	327	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 281-288 - best focus image product
		3821MH0002270001400328000	328	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 281-288 - range map product
		3821MH0002270001400329000	329	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 271-278 - best focus image product
		3821MH0002270001400330000	330	target Itha_Grande - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3821 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 271-278 - range map product

updated: 10_May_2023

Sol 3823 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		9 May 23		
camera positions:	4	Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	4	CDPID:		
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total focus merge products:	0			
total parent images + focus merge products:	4			
summary of MAHLI activities: Drill preparation activities at the planned Ubajara sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Ubajara sample discard pile.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	intended Ubajara Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~23 cm standoff	3823MH00190001400331C00	331	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 23 cm
		3823MH00190001400332C00	332	intended Ubajara drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 23 cm
mN00122	intended Ubajara Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~35 mm standoff	3823MH00122001400333C00	333	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Ubajara drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 35 mm
		3823MH00122001400334C00	334	intended Ubajara drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 35 mm

updated: 22_May_2023

Sol 3834 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-May-23
camera position	2
total parent images	15
focus merges performed	1
total focus merge products	2
total parent images + focus merge products	16

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Ubajara drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Ubajara drill hole drilled on Sol 3823 ~24 cm standoff	3834MH0001970001400335C00	335	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Ubajara - drilled sol 3823 - standoff near 24 cm
		3834MH0001970011400336C00	336	drill hole in rock named Ubajara - drilled sol 3823 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00774	Ubajara drill hole drilled on Sol 3823 ~9 cm standoff	3834MH0007740001400337C00	337	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Ubajara - drilled sol 3823 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 9 cm
		3834MH0007740011400338C00	338	drill hole in rock named Ubajara - drilled sol 3823 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 9 cm
mN00152	Ubajara drill cuttings ~45 mm standoff	3834MH0001520001400339C00	339	autofocus sub-frame for Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm
		3834MH0001520011400340C00	340	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm
		3834MH0001520021400341C00	341	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520031400342C00	342	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520041400343C00	343	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520051400344C00	344	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520061400345C00	345	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520071400346C00	346	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520081400347C00	347	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3834MH0001520091400348C00	348	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00258	Focus Merge	3834MH0002580001400349R00	349	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3834 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 341-348 - best focus image product
		3834MH0002580001400350R00	350	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3834 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 341-348 - range map product

updated: 22_May_2023

Sol 3835 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-May-23
camera position	0
total parent images	2
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	2

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Ubajara drill hole cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00122	Ubajara drill cuttings ~45 mm standoff	3835MH00122001400351C00	351	autoFocus sub-frame for Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm
		3835MH00122001400352C00	352	Ubajara drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm

updated: 27_October_2023

Sol 3837 - MAHI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	23-May-23	
		camera position	51	Image ID:
		total parent images	3	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images - focus merge products	12	
summary of MAHI activities		During the day, MAHI images that correspond to CDPID 3461 through 4854 (data from Sol 3725-3801) were deleted from the MAHI DEA non-volatile memory storage. MAHI also imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the DRT-brushed target Apetina. The corresponding focus stack images for the day-time imaging were merged as well. At night, MAHI re-imaged the DRT-brushed target Apetina using different combinations of the LEDs, including ultraviolet to seek fluorescence.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~5 cm standoff	3837MH00095001400353CD	353	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3837MH00095001400354CD	354	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00190	Apetina after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3837MH00190001400355CD	355	autofocus sub-frame for target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3837MH00190001400356CD	356	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Apetina after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3837MH00182001400357CD	357	autofocus sub-frame for target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3837MH00182001400358CD	358	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3837MH00182001400359CD	359	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400360CD	360	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400361CD	361	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400362CD	362	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400363CD	363	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400364CD	364	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400365CD	365	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400366CD	366	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Apetina after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3837MH00182001400367CD	367	autofocus sub-frame for target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3837MH00182001400368CD	368	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3837MH00182001400369CD	369	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400370CD	370	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400371CD	371	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400372CD	372	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400373CD	373	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400374CD	374	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400375CD	375	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00182001400376CD	376	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Apetina after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3837MH00184001400377CD	377	autofocus sub-frame for target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3837MH00184001400378CD	378	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3837MH00184001400379CD	379	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00184001400380CD	380	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00184001400381CD	381	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00184001400382CD	382	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00184001400383CD	383	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00184001400384CD	384	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3837MH00193001400385CD	385	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00193001400386CD	386	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH00193001400387CD	387	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 379-384 - best focus image product
		3837MH00193001400388CD	388	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 379-384 - range map product
		3837MH00193001400389CD	389	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 369-376 - best focus image product
		3837MH00193001400390CD	390	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 369-376 - range map product
mN00081	Apetina after DRT night imaging ~5 cm standoff	3837MH000861001400391CD	391	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 359-366 - best focus image product
		3837MH000861001400392CD	392	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 359-366 - range map product
		3837MH000861001400393CD	393	autofocus sub-frame for target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on
		3837MH000861001400394CD	394	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 1 white LEDs on
		3837MH000861001400395CD	395	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on
		3837MH000861001400396CD	396	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - alternative auto-exposure
		3837MH000861001400397CD	397	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - all white LEDs on
		3837MH000861001400398CD	398	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - ultraviolet LEDs on with 30-second manual exposure
		3837MH000861001400399CD	399	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - dark frame - no LEDs on - 30-second manual exposure
		3837MH000861001400400CD	400	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - ultraviolet LEDs on with 60-second manual exposure
		3837MH000861001400401CD	401	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - dark frame - no LEDs on - 60-second manual exposure
		3837MH000861001400402CD	402	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400403CD	403	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400404CD	404	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400405CD	405	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400406CD	406	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400407CD	407	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400408CD	408	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3837MH000861001400409CD	409	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 25_May_2023

Sol 3838 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-May-23	Image ID:		
camera position:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
total parent images:	0	CDPID:		
focus merges performed:	1	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total focus merge products:	2			
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
summary of MAHLI activities:	Focus stack images from the Sol 3837 night imaging of Apetina were merged.			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00258	Focus Merge	3838MH002580001400410R00	410	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 402-409 - best focus image product
		3838MH002580001400411S00	411	target Apetina - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm - night imaging - group 2 white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 3837 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 402-409 - range map product

updated: 26_May_2023

Sol 3839 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-May-23
camera position	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Zepaqira a and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Zepaqira after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3839MH001900014004120D	412	autoFocus sub-frame for target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3839MH001900014004130D	413	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Zepaqira after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3839MH001680014004140D	414	autoFocus sub-frame for target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3839MH001680014004150D	415	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3839MH001680014004160D	416	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004170D	417	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004180D	418	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004190D	419	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004200D	420	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004210D	421	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004220D	422	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004230D	423	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Zepaqira after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3839MH001680014004240D	424	autoFocus sub-frame for target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3839MH001680014004250D	425	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3839MH001680014004260D	426	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004270D	427	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004280D	428	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004290D	429	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004300D	430	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004310D	431	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004320D	432	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH001680014004330D	433	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Zepaqira after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3839MH007430014004340D	434	autoFocus sub-frame for target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3839MH007430014004350D	435	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3839MH007430014004360D	436	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004370D	437	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004380D	438	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004390D	439	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004400D	440	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004410D	441	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004420D	442	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3839MH007430014004430D	443	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3839MH001930014004440D	444	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 426-443 - best focus image product
		3839MH001930014004450D	445	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 426-443 - range map product
		3839MH001930014004460D	446	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 426-433 - best focus image product
		3839MH001930014004470D	447	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 426-433 - range map product
		3839MH001930014004480D	448	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 416-423 - best focus image product
		3839MH001930014004490D	449	target Zepaqira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3839 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 416-423 - range map product

updated: 02_June_2023

Sol 3845 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	31-May-23
camera position	0
total parent images	55
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	55

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities				MAHLI acquired a 1x3 mosaic on the target Cumbal and then imaged the DRT-brushed target Cujubim.
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00172	Cumbal mosaic position 1 of 2 ~18 cm standoff	3845MH00172001400450C00	450	autofocus sub-frame for target Cumbal - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 18 cm
		3845MH00172001400451C00	451	target Cumbal - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 18 cm
mN00172	Cumbal mosaic position 2 of 2 ~18 cm standoff	3845MH00172001400452C00	452	autofocus sub-frame for target Cumbal - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 18 cm
		3845MH00172001400453C00	453	target Cumbal - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 18 cm
mN00190	Cujubim after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3845MH00190001400454C00	454	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 25 cm
		3845MH00190001400455C00	455	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Cujubim after DRT APXS spot 3 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3845MH00182001400456C00	456	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400457C00	457	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400458C00	458	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400459C00	459	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400460C00	460	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400461C00	461	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400462C00	462	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400463C00	463	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400464C00	464	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400465C00	465	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Cujubim after DRT APXS spot 3 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3845MH00182001400466C00	466	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400467C00	467	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400468C00	468	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400469C00	469	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400470C00	470	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400471C00	471	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400472C00	472	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400473C00	473	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400474C00	474	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400475C00	475	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Cujubim after DRT APXS spot 3 stereo-1 ~2 cm standoff	3845MH00184001400476C00	476	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm
		3845MH00184001400477C00	477	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm
		3845MH00184001400478C00	478	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400479C00	479	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400480C00	480	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400481C00	481	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400482C00	482	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400483C00	483	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400484C00	484	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00184001400485C00	485	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Cujubim after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3845MH00182001400486C00	486	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400487C00	487	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400488C00	488	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400489C00	489	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400490C00	490	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400491C00	491	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400492C00	492	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400493C00	493	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400494C00	494	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400495C00	495	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Cujubim after DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3845MH00182001400496C00	496	autofocus sub-frame for target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400497C00	497	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3845MH00182001400498C00	498	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400499C00	499	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400500C00	500	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400501C00	501	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400502C00	502	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400503C00	503	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400504C00	504	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3845MH00182001400505C00	505	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 02_June_2023

Sol 3846 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	1-Jun-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3845 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3846MH0002270001400506R00	506	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 498-505 - best focus image product
		3846MH0002270001400507500	507	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 498-505 - range map product
		3846MH0002270001400508R00	508	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 488-495 - best focus image product
		3846MH0002270001400509500	509	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 488-495 - range map product
		3846MH0002270001400510R00	510	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 478-485 - best focus image product
		3846MH0002270001400511500	511	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 478-485 - range map product
		3846MH0002270001400512R00	512	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 468-475 - best focus image product
		3846MH0002270001400513500	513	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 468-475 - range map product
		3846MH0002270001400514R00	514	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 458-465 - best focus image product
		3846MH0002270001400515500	515	target Cujubim - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 3 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3845 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 458-465 - range map product

updated: 07_june_2023

Sol 3851 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	7 Jun 23
camera position:	6
total parent images:	33
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Aporema and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Aforema after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3851MH0019000140051600D	516	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3851MH0019000140051700D	517	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Aforema after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3851MH0016800140051800D	518	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3851MH0016800140051900D	519	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3851MH00168002140052000D	520	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052100D	521	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052200D	522	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052300D	523	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052400D	524	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052500D	525	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052600D	526	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168002140052700D	527	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Aforema after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3851MH00168003140052800D	528	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3851MH00168003140052900D	529	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3851MH00168003140053000D	530	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053100D	531	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053200D	532	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053300D	533	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053400D	534	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053500D	535	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053600D	536	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH00168003140053700D	537	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Aforema after DRT ~5 mm standoff	3851MH00084800140053800D	538	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3851MH00084800140053900D	539	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3851MH000848002140054000D	540	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054100D	541	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054200D	542	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054300D	543	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054400D	544	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054500D	545	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054600D	546	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3851MH000848002140054700D	547	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00289	Focus Merges	3851MH0019300140054800D	548	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 540-547 - best focus image product
		3851MH0019300140054900D	549	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 540-547 - range map product
		3851MH0019300140055000D	550	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 530-537 - best focus image product
		3851MH0019300140055100D	551	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 530-537 - range map product
		3851MH0019300140055200D	552	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 520-527 - best focus image product
3851MH0019300140055300D	553	target Aporema - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3851 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 520-527 - range map product		

updated: 27_October_2023

Sol 3853 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	9-Jun-23
camera position	6
total parent images	47
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	55

MAHLI image the targets Massaco and Saul. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00862	Massaco stereo-1 ~23 cm standoff	3853MH00086200140054420	554	autoFocus sub-frame for target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3853MH00086200140055520	555	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3853MH00086200140056620	556	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3853MH00086200140057720	557	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140058820	558	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140059920	559	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140061020	560	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140062120	561	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140063220	562	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140064320	563	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140065420	564	target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140066520	565	autoFocus sub-frame for target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3853MH00086200140067620	566	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3853MH00086200140068720	567	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00862	Massaco stereo-2 ~23 cm standoff	3853MH00086200140069820	568	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140070920	569	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140072020	570	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140073120	571	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140074220	572	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140075320	573	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140076420	574	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00086200140077520	575	target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Saul ~24 cm standoff	3853MH0007600140057620	576	autoFocus sub-frame for target Saul - standoff near 24 cm
				3853MH0007600140057720	577	target Saul - standoff near 24 cm
				3853MH0007600140057820	578	target Saul - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				3853MH0007600140057920	579	autoFocus sub-frame for target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		mNI00723	Saul stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3853MH00072300140058020	580	target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
				3853MH00072300140058120	581	target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
3853MH00072300140058220	582			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058320	583			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058420	584			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058520	585			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058620	586			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058720	587			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058820	588			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3853MH00072300140058920	589			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00723	Saul stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff			3853MH00072300140059020	590	autoFocus sub-frame for target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3853MH00072300140059120	591	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3853MH00072300140059220	592	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				3853MH00072300140059320	593	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3853MH00072300140059420	594	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140059520	595	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140059620	596	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140059720	597	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140059820	598	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140059920	599	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3853MH00072300140060020	600	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00817	Focus Merges	3853MH000817000140060100	601	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 593-600 - best focus image product
				3853MH000817000140060200	602	target Saul - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 593-600 - range map product
				3853MH000817000140060300	603	target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 582-589 - best focus image product
3853MH000817000140060400	604			target Saul - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 582-589 - range map product		
3853MH000817000140060500	605			target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 568-575 - best focus image product		
3853MH000817000140060600	606			target Massaco - stereo-2 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 568-575 - range map product		
3853MH000817000140060700	607			target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 557-564 - best focus image product		
3853MH000817000140060800	608			target Massaco - stereo-1 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3853 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 557-564 - range map product		

updated: 12_June_2023

Sol 3855 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15_Jun-23
camera position	4
total parent images	5
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	5

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities:
 At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	3855MH0003120001400609C00	609	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		3855MH0003120011400610C00	610	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
m1N00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3855MH0003260001400611C00	611	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
m1N00325	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3855MH0003260001400612C00	612	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
m1N00328	~19 cm above open CheMin inlet	3855MH0003280001400613C00	613	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 19_June_2023

Sol 3858 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16 Jun 23
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Terabito and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002168	Terabito after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3858MH001680021400614C00	614	autofocus sub-frame for target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3858MH001680021400615C00	615	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3858MH001680021400616C00	616	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400617C00	617	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400618C00	618	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400619C00	619	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400620C00	620	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400621C00	621	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400622C00	622	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400623C00	623	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH001680021400624C00	624	autofocus sub-frame for target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3858MH001680021400625C00	625	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3858MH001680021400626C00	626	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3858MH001680021400627C00	627	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400628C00	628	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400629C00	629	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400630C00	630	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400631C00	631	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400632C00	632	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3858MH001680021400633C00	633	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN002743	Terabito after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3858MH007430021400634C00	634	autofocus sub-frame for target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3858MH007430021400635C00	635	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3858MH007430021400636C00	636	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400637C00	637	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400638C00	638	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400639C00	639	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400640C00	640	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400641C00	641	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400642C00	642	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3858MH007430021400643C00	643	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002190	Terabito after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3858MH001900021400644C00	644	autofocus sub-frame for target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3858MH001900021400645C00	645	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002193	Focus Merges	3858MH001930021400646R00	646	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 616-643 - best focus image product
		3858MH001930021400647S00	647	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 616-643 - range map product
		3858MH001930021400648R00	648	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 626-633 - best focus image product
		3858MH001930021400649S00	649	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 626-633 - range map product
		3858MH001930021400650R00	650	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 616-623 - best focus image product
		3858MH001930021400651S00	651	target Terabito - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3858 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 616-623 - range map product

Sol 3859 - MAHI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	25 Jun 23	
		camera position	85	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	85	
MAHI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding. MAHI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Rio_Madeira and the target Macapa.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +121.5° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	3859MH000712001400652C00	652	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 9 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		3859MH000712001400653C00	653	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		3859MH000712001400654C00	654	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		3859MH000712001400655C00	655	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 268 mm
		3859MH000712001400656C00	656	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus
mN00453	sky flats - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +121.5° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck	3859MH000453001400657C00	657	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm
		3859MH000453001400658C00	658	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm
		3859MH000453001400659C00	659	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm
		3859MH000453001400660C00	660	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm
		3859MH000453001400661C00	661	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm
mN00453	sky flats - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +121.5° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	3859MH000453001400662C00	662	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus
		3859MH000453001400663C00	663	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000453001400664C00	664	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000453001400665C00	665	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000453001400666C00	666	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
mN00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +121.5° azimuth, +30° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	3859MH000712001400667C00	667	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 633 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000712001400668C00	668	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000712001400669C00	669	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000712001400670C00	670	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
		3859MH000712001400671C00	671	MAHI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol
mN00190	Rio_Madeira after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3859MH000190001400674C00	674	autoFocus sub-frame for target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3859MH000190001400675C00	675	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3859MH00182001400676C00	676	autoFocus sub-frame for target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH00182001400677C00	677	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH00182001400678C00	678	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Rio_Madeira after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3859MH00182001400679C00	679	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400680C00	680	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400681C00	681	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400682C00	682	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400683C00	683	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Rio_Madeira after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3859MH00182001400684C00	684	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400685C00	685	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400686C00	686	autoFocus sub-frame for target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH00182001400687C00	687	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH00182001400688C00	688	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Rio_Madeira after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3859MH000743001400689C00	689	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400689C00	689	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400690C00	690	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400691C00	691	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH00182001400692C00	692	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Rio_Madeira after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3859MH000743001400693C00	693	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400694C00	694	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400695C00	695	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400696C00	696	autoFocus sub-frame for target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3859MH000743001400697C00	697	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
mN00743	Rio_Madeira after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3859MH000743001400698C00	698	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400699C00	699	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400700C00	700	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400701C00	701	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000743001400702C00	702	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00678	Macapa ~25 cm standoff	3859MH000678001400703C00	703	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400704C00	704	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400705C00	705	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400706C00	706	autoFocus sub-frame for target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm
		3859MH000678001400707C00	707	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm
mN00678	Macapa ~25 cm standoff	3859MH000678001400708C00	708	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3859MH000678001400709C00	709	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400710C00	710	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400711C00	711	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400712C00	712	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00678	Macapa ~25 cm standoff	3859MH000678001400713C00	713	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400714C00	714	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400715C00	715	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH000678001400716C00	716	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

mh00306	Macapa stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3859MH0030600140071700	717	autofocus sub-frame for target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH0030600140071800	718	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH0030600140071900	719	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072000	720	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072100	721	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072200	722	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072300	723	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072400	724	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140072500	725	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3859MH0030600140072600	726	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mh00306	Macapa stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3859MH0030600140072700	727	autofocus sub-frame for target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH0030600140072800	728	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3859MH0030600140072900	729	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073000	730	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073100	731	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073200	732	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073300	733	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073400	734	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3859MH0030600140073500	735	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3859MH0030600140073600	736	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 19_June_2023

Sol 3860 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16_Jun_23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3859 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	3860MH000163000140073700	737	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 729-736 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140073850	738	target Macapa - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 729-736 - range map product
		3860MH000163000140073900	739	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 719-726 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140074050	740	target Macapa - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 719-726 - range map product
		3860MH000163000140074100	741	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 709-716 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140074250	742	target Macapa - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 709-716 - range map product
		3860MH000163000140074300	743	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 698-705 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140074450	744	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 698-705 - range map product
		3860MH000163000140074500	745	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 688-695 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140074650	746	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 688-695 - range map product
		3860MH000163000140074700	747	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 678-685 - best focus image product
		3860MH000163000140074850	748	target Rio_Madeira - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3859 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 678-685 - range map product

updated: 20_june_2023

Sol 3864 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20_jun_23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3862 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3864MH001630001400813000	813	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 805-812 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400814500	814	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 805-812 - range map product
		3864MH001630001400815000	815	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 795-802 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400816500	816	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 795-802 - range map product
		3864MH001630001400817000	817	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 785-792 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400818500	818	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 785-792 - range map product
		3864MH001630001400819000	819	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 775-782 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400820500	820	target Surpressa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 775-782 - range map product
		3864MH001630001400821000	821	target Surpressa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 763-770 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400822500	822	target Surpressa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 763-770 - range map product
		3864MH001630001400823000	823	target Surpressa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 753-760 - best focus image product
		3864MH001630001400824500	824	target Surpressa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3862 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 753-760 - range map product

mH00182	Kastria_Spring after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3866MH00182001400895C00	889	autofocus sub-frame for target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3866MH00182001400890C00	890	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3866MH00182001400893C00	891	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400892C00	892	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400893C00	893	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400894C00	894	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400895C00	895	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400896C00	896	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400897C00	897	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3866MH00182001400898C00	898	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00302	Kastria_Spring after DRT APXS spot 1 ~7 cm standoff	3866MH00302001400895C00	899	autofocus sub-frame for target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm
		3866MH00302001400900C00	900	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm
		3866MH00302001400903C00	901	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400902C00	902	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400903C00	903	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400904C00	904	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400905C00	905	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400906C00	906	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00302001400907C00	907	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3866MH00302001400908C00	908	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00182	Kastria_Spring after DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3866MH00182001400909C00	909	autofocus sub-frame for target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3866MH00182001400910C00	910	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3866MH00182001400911C00	911	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400912C00	912	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400913C00	913	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400914C00	914	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400915C00	915	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400916C00	916	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400917C00	917	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3866MH00182001400918C00	918	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 26_June_2023

Sol 3867 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jan 23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3866 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPVID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	3867MH000536000140091900	919	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 911-918 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140092050	920	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 911-918 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140092100	921	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 901-908 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140092250	922	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 901-908 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140092300	923	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 891-898 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140092450	924	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 891-898 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140092500	925	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 881-888 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140092650	926	target Kastria_Spring - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 881-888 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140092700	927	target Feneos - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 869-876 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140092850	928	target Feneos - mosaic position 5 of 5 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 869-876 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140092900	929	target Feneos - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 859-866 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140093050	930	target Feneos - mosaic position 4 of 5 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 859-866 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140093100	931	target Feneos - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 849-856 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140093250	932	target Feneos - mosaic position 3 of 5 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 849-856 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140093300	933	target Feneos - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 839-846 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140093450	934	target Feneos - mosaic position 2 of 5 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 839-846 - range map product
		3867MH000536000140093500	935	target Feneos - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 829-836 - best focus image product
		3867MH000536000140093650	936	target Feneos - mosaic position 1 of 5 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3866 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 829-836 - range map product

updated: 31_July_2023

Sol 3871 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Jun-23
camera positions	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Lousoi and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Lousoi after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3871MH00190001400979Z00	937	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3871MH00190001400938C00	938	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Lousoi after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3871MH00182001400939C00	939	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3871MH00182001400940C00	940	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3871MH00182001400941C00	941	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400942C00	942	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400943C00	943	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400944C00	944	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400945C00	945	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400946C00	946	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400947C00	947	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400948C00	948	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Lousoi after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3871MH00182001400949C00	949	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3871MH00182001400950C00	950	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3871MH00182001400951C00	951	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400952C00	952	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400953C00	953	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400954C00	954	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400955C00	955	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400956C00	956	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400957C00	957	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00182001400958C00	958	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00176	Lousoi after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3871MH00176001400959C00	959	autoFocus sub-frame for target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3871MH00176001400960C00	960	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3871MH00176001400961C00	961	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00176001400962C00	962	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00176001400963C00	963	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00176001400964C00	964	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00176001400965C00	965	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3871MH00176001400966C00	966	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3871MH00193001400969K00	969	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 961-968 - best focus image product
		3871MH00193001400970K00	970	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 961-968 - range map product
		3871MH00193001400971K00	971	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 951-958 - best focus image product
		3871MH00193001400972K00	972	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 951-958 - range map product
		3871MH00193001400973K00	973	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 941-948 - best focus image product
		3871MH00193001400974K00	974	target Lousoi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3871 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 941-948 - range map product

updated: 27_October_2023

Sol 3873 - MAHLI Images

		acquired (performed date(s))	29 Jun 23	
		camera position	7	Image ID:
		total parent images	54	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	64	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Madero and the target Vesini. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Madero after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3873MH00190001400979ZC0	975	autofocus sub-frame for target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3873MH00190001400979ZC0	976	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Madero after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3873MH00168001400979ZC0	977	autofocus sub-frame for target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00168001400979ZC0	978	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00168001400979ZC0	979	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400980ZC0	980	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400981ZC0	981	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400982ZC0	982	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400983ZC0	983	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400984ZC0	984	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400985ZC0	985	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400986ZC0	986	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Madero after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3873MH00168001400987ZC0	987	autofocus sub-frame for target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00168001400988ZC0	988	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00168001400989ZC0	989	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400990ZC0	990	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400991ZC0	991	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400992ZC0	992	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400993ZC0	993	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400994ZC0	994	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400995ZC0	995	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00168001400996ZC0	996	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Madero after DRT ~15 mm standoff	3873MH00184001400997ZC0	997	autofocus sub-frame for target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3873MH00184001400998ZC0	998	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3873MH00184001400999ZC0	999	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401000ZC0	1000	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401001ZC0	1001	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401002ZC0	1002	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401003ZC0	1003	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401004ZC0	1004	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401005ZC0	1005	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00184001401006ZC0	1006	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Vesini ~24 cm standoff	3873MH00190001401007ZC0	1007	autofocus sub-frame for target Vesini - standoff near 24 cm
		3873MH00190001401008ZC0	1008	target Vesini - standoff near 24 cm
mN00152	Vesini stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3873MH00152001401009ZC0	1009	autofocus sub-frame for target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00152001401010ZC0	1010	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00152001401011ZC0	1011	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401012ZC0	1012	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401013ZC0	1013	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401014ZC0	1014	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401015ZC0	1015	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401016ZC0	1016	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401017ZC0	1017	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401018ZC0	1018	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00152	Vesini stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3873MH00152001401019ZC0	1019	autofocus sub-frame for target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00152001401020ZC0	1020	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3873MH00152001401021ZC0	1021	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401022ZC0	1022	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401023ZC0	1023	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401024ZC0	1024	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401025ZC0	1025	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401026ZC0	1026	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401027ZC0	1027	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3873MH00152001401028ZC0	1028	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3873MH0002270001401029Z00	1029	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1021-1028 - best focus image product
		3873MH0002270001401030Z00	1030	target Vesini - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1021-1028 - range map product
		3873MH0002270001401031Z00	1031	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1011-1018 - best focus image product
		3873MH0002270001401032Z00	1032	target Vesini - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1011-1018 - range map product
		3873MH0002270001401033Z00	1033	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 999-1006 - best focus image product
		3873MH0002270001401034Z00	1034	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 999-1006 - range map product
		3873MH0002270001401035Z00	1035	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 989-996 - best focus image product
		3873MH0002270001401036Z00	1036	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 989-996 - range map product
		3873MH0002270001401037Z00	1037	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 979-986 - best focus image product
		3873MH0002270001401038Z00	1038	target Madero - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3873 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 979-986 - range map product

mNH00182	Analipsi stereo-2 -3 cm standoff	3877MH0001820001401105C00	1105	autofocus sub-frame for target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3877MH0001820011401106C00	1106	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3877MH0001820021401107C00	1107	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401108C00	1108	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401109C00	1109	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401110C00	1110	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401111C00	1111	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401112C00	1112	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3877MH0001820021401113C00	1113	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3877MH0001820021401114C00	1114	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNH00171	Focus Merge	3877MH0001710001401115R00	1115	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1107-1114 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401116S00	1116	target Analipsi - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1107-1114 - range map product
		3877MH0001710001401117R00	1117	target Analipsi - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1097-1104 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401118S00	1118	target Analipsi - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1097-1104 - range map product
		3877MH0001710001401119R00	1119	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1085-1092 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401120S00	1120	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1085-1092 - range map product
		3877MH0001710001401121R00	1121	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1075-1082 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401122S00	1122	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1075-1082 - range map product
		3877MH0001710001401123R00	1123	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1065-1072 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401124S00	1124	target Trapeza - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1065-1072 - range map product
		3877MH0001710001401125R00	1125	target Trapeza - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1053-1060 - best focus image product
		3877MH0001710001401126S00	1126	target Trapeza - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1053-1060 - range map product

updated: 10_August_2023

Sol 3878 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6 Jul 23	Image ID:	
camera position:	25	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	25	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	1	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	2		
total parent images + focus merge products:	27		

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images for Sol 3877 stereo-1 before DRT imaging of Trapeza were merged. MAHLI imageid 2 360' of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00071	Focus Merge	3878MH00017J0001401127900	1127	target Trapeza - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1043-1050 - best focus image product
		3878MH00017J0001401128500	1128	target Trapeza - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3877 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1043-1050 - range map product
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3878MH0007690011401129001	1129	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3878MH0007700011401130E01	1130	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3878MH0007710011401131E01	1131	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3878MH0007720011401132E01	1132	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3878MH0007690011401133E01	1133	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3878MH0007700011401134E01	1134	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3878MH0007710011401135E01	1135	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3878MH0007720011401136E01	1136	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3878MH0007690011401137E01	1137	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3878MH0007700011401138E01	1138	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3878MH0007710011401139E01	1139	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3878MH0007720011401140E01	1140	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3878MH0007690011401141E01	1141	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3878MH0007700011401142E01	1142	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3878MH0007710011401143E01	1143	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3878MH0007720011401144E01	1144	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3878MH0007690011401145E01	1145	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3878MH0007700011401146E01	1146	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3878MH0007710011401147E01	1147	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3878MH0007720011401148E01	1148	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3878 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

mnh00163	Focus Merge	3880MH001630001401211800	1211	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1203-1210 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401212500	1212	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1203-1210 - range map product
		3880MH001630001401213800	1213	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1193-1200 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401214500	1214	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1193-1200 - range map product
		3880MH001630001401215800	1215	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1183-1190 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401216500	1216	target Xerocambos - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1183-1190 - range map product
		3880MH001630001401217800	1217	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1173-1180 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401218500	1218	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1173-1180 - range map product
		3880MH001630001401219800	1219	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1163-1170 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401220500	1220	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1163-1170 - range map product
		3880MH001630001401221800	1221	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1153-1160 - best focus image product
		3880MH001630001401222500	1222	target Roghi - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3880 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1153-1160 - range map product

updated: 14_July_2023

Sol 3885 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	13 Jul 23
camera position:	2
total parent images:	23
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	26

MAHLI imaged the target Planitero and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Planitero ~25 cm standoff	3885MH00190001401223C0D	1223	autoFocus sub-frame for target Planitero - standoff near 25 cm
		3885MH00190001401224C0D	1224	target Planitero - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Planitero stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3885MH00168001401225C0D	1225	autoFocus sub-frame for target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3885MH00168001401226C0D	1226	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3885MH00168001401227C0D	1227	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401228C0D	1228	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401229C0D	1229	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401230C0D	1230	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401231C0D	1231	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401232C0D	1232	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401233C0D	1233	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401234C0D	1234	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Planitero stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3885MH00168001401235C0D	1235	autoFocus sub-frame for target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3885MH00168001401236C0D	1236	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3885MH00168001401237C0D	1237	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401238C0D	1238	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401239C0D	1239	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401240C0D	1240	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401241C0D	1241	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401242C0D	1242	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401243C0D	1243	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3885MH00168001401244C0D	1244	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3885MH00265001401245R0D	1245	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3885 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1237-1244 - best focus image product
		3885MH00265001401246S0D	1246	target Planitero - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3885 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1237-1244 - range map product
		3885MH00265001401247R0D	1247	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3885 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1227-1234 - best focus image product
		3885MH00265001401248S0D	1248	target Planitero - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3885 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1227-1234 - range map product

updated: 17_July_2023

Sol 3887 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-04-2023/18-04-2023
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Sounion and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sounion after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3887MH001900014012490D0	1249	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3887MH001900014012500D0	1250	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Sounion after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3887MH001680014012510D0	1251	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3887MH001680014012520D0	1252	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3887MH001680014012530D0	1253	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012540D0	1254	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012550D0	1255	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012560D0	1256	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012570D0	1257	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012580D0	1258	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012590D0	1259	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012600D0	1260	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sounion after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3887MH001680014012610D0	1261	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3887MH001680014012620D0	1262	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3887MH001680014012630D0	1263	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012640D0	1264	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012650D0	1265	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012660D0	1266	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012670D0	1267	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012680D0	1268	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012690D0	1269	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH001680014012700D0	1270	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00796	Sounion after DRT ~15 mm standoff	3887MH007960014012710D0	1271	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3887MH007960014012720D0	1272	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3887MH007960014012730D0	1273	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012740D0	1274	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012750D0	1275	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012760D0	1276	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012770D0	1277	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012780D0	1278	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012790D0	1279	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3887MH007960014012800D0	1280	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3887MH001930014012810D0	1281	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1273-1280 - best focus image product
		3887MH001930014012820D0	1282	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1273-1280 - range map product
		3887MH001930014012830D0	1283	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1263-1270 - best focus image product
		3887MH001930014012840D0	1284	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1263-1270 - range map product
		3887MH001930014012850D0	1285	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1253-1260 - best focus image product
		3887MH001930014012860D0	1286	target Sounion - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 3887 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1253-1260 - range map product

updated: 17_May_2023

Sol 3890 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	27 Jul 23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3889 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3890MH0002270001401347800	1347	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1339-1346 - best focus image product
		3890MH0002270001401348500	1348	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1339-1346 - range map product
		3890MH0002270001401349900	1349	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1323-1330 - best focus image product
		3890MH0002270001401350500	1350	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1323-1330 - range map product
		3890MH0002270001401351900	1351	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1313-1320 - best focus image product
		3890MH0002270001401352500	1352	target Zachlorou - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1313-1320 - range map product
		3890MH0002270001401353900	1353	target Thermopylae - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1301-1308 - best focus image product
		3890MH0002270001401354500	1354	target Thermopylae - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1301-1308 - range map product
		3890MH0002270001401355900	1355	target Thermopylae - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1291-1298 - best focus image product
		3890MH0002270001401356500	1356	target Thermopylae - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3889 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1291-1298 - range map product

updated: 20_July_2023

Sol 3892 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	28 Jul 23
camera position:	6
total parent images:	33
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	39

MAHLI imaged the target Nasia and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Nasia ~25 cm standoff	3892MH00190001401357CDD	1357	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nasia - standoff near 25 cm
		3892MH00190001401358CDD	1358	target Nasia - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Nasia stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3892MH00173001401359CDD	1359	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3892MH00173001401360CDD	1360	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3892MH00173001401361CDD	1361	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401362CDD	1362	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401363CDD	1363	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401364CDD	1364	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401365CDD	1365	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401366CDD	1366	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401367CDD	1367	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401368CDD	1368	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Nasia stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3892MH00173001401369CDD	1369	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3892MH00173001401370CDD	1370	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3892MH00173001401371CDD	1371	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401372CDD	1372	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401373CDD	1373	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401374CDD	1374	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401375CDD	1375	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401376CDD	1376	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401377CDD	1377	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00173001401378CDD	1378	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00796	Nasia ~1 cm standoff	3892MH00796001401379CDD	1379	autoFocus sub-frame for target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm
		3892MH00796001401380CDD	1380	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm
		3892MH00796001401381CDD	1381	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401382CDD	1382	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401383CDD	1383	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401384CDD	1384	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401385CDD	1385	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401386CDD	1386	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401387CDD	1387	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3892MH00796001401388CDD	1388	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3892MH00193001401389CDD	1389	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1381-1388 - best focus image product
		3892MH00193001401390CDD	1390	target Nasia - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1381-1388 - range map product
		3892MH00193001401391CDD	1391	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1371-1378 - best focus image product
		3892MH00193001401392CDD	1392	target Nasia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1371-1378 - range map product
		3892MH00193001401393CDD	1393	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - best focus image product
		3892MH00193001401394CDD	1394	target Nasia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3892 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - range map product

updated: 24_July_2023

Sol 3895 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23 Jul 23
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the target Rio_Javari and the DRT-brushed target La_Trintite.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Rio_Javari ~24 cm standoff	3895MH00190001401395C00	1395	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Javari - standoff near 24 cm
		3895MH00190001401396C00	1396	target Rio_Javari - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Rio_Javari stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3895MH00168001401397C00	1397	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3895MH00168001401398C00	1398	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3895MH00168001401399C00	1399	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401400C00	1400	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401401C00	1401	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401402C00	1402	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401403C00	1403	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401404C00	1404	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401405C00	1405	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401406C00	1406	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Rio_Javari stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3895MH00168001401407C00	1407	autofocus sub-frame for target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3895MH00168001401408C00	1408	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3895MH00168001401409C00	1409	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401410C00	1410	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401411C00	1411	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401412C00	1412	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401413C00	1413	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401414C00	1414	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401415C00	1415	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401416C00	1416	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	La_Trintite after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3895MH00190001401417C00	1417	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3895MH00190001401418C00	1418	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	La_Trintite after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3895MH00168001401419C00	1419	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3895MH00168001401420C00	1420	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3895MH00168001401421C00	1421	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401422C00	1422	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401423C00	1423	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401424C00	1424	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401425C00	1425	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401426C00	1426	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401427C00	1427	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401428C00	1428	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	La_Trintite after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3895MH00168001401429C00	1429	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3895MH00168001401430C00	1430	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3895MH00168001401431C00	1431	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401432C00	1432	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401433C00	1433	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401434C00	1434	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401435C00	1435	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401436C00	1436	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401437C00	1437	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00168001401438C00	1438	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	La_Trintite after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3895MH00743001401439C00	1439	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3895MH00743001401440C00	1440	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3895MH00743001401441C00	1441	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401442C00	1442	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401443C00	1443	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401444C00	1444	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401445C00	1445	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401446C00	1446	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401447C00	1447	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3895MH00743001401448C00	1448	target La_Trintite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 24_July_2023

Sol 3897 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	24 Jul 23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3895 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3897MH002270001401449R00	1449	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1441-1448 - best focus image product
		3897MH002270001401450S00	1450	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1441-1448 - range map product
		3897MH002270001401451R00	1451	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1431-1438 - best focus image product
		3897MH002270001401452S00	1452	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1431-1438 - range map product
		3897MH002270001401453R00	1453	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1421-1428 - best focus image product
		3897MH002270001401454S00	1454	target Ia_Trinite - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1421-1428 - range map product
		3897MH002270001401455R00	1455	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1409-1416 - best focus image product
		3897MH002270001401456S00	1456	target Rio_Javari - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1409-1416 - range map product
		3897MH002270001401457R00	1457	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1399-1406 - best focus image product
		3897MH002270001401458S00	1458	target Rio_Javari - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3895 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1399-1406 - range map product

updated: 01_August_2023

Sol 3898 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25 Jul 23
camera position	6
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	40

MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor and the DRT - brushed target Mamore. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3898MH000950014014930D	1459	autoFocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3898MH000950014014600D	1460	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00190	Mamore after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3898MH001900014014610D	1461	autoFocus sub-frame for target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3898MH001900014014620D	1462	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Mamore after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3898MH001820014014630D	1463	autoFocus sub-frame for target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3898MH001820014014640D	1464	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3898MH001820014014650D	1465	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014660D	1466	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014670D	1467	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014680D	1468	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014690D	1469	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014700D	1470	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014710D	1471	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014720D	1472	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Mamore after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3898MH001820014014730D	1473	autoFocus sub-frame for target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3898MH001820014014740D	1474	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3898MH001820014014750D	1475	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014760D	1476	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014770D	1477	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014780D	1478	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014790D	1479	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014800D	1480	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014810D	1481	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001820014014820D	1482	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Mamore after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3898MH001840014014830D	1483	autoFocus sub-frame for target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3898MH001840014014840D	1484	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3898MH001840014014850D	1485	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014860D	1486	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014870D	1487	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014880D	1488	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014890D	1489	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014900D	1490	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014910D	1491	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3898MH001840014014920D	1492	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3898MH001930014014930D	1493	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1485-1492 - best focus image product
		3898MH001930014014940D	1494	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1485-1492 - range map product
		3898MH001930014014950D	1495	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1475-1482 - best focus image product
		3898MH001930014014960D	1496	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1475-1482 - range map product
		3898MH001930014014970D	1497	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1465-1472 - best focus image product
		3898MH001930014014980D	1498	target Mamore - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3898 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1465-1472 - range map product

updated: 02_August_2023

Sol 3899 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jul 23
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	64

MAHLI images of the targets Guinia and Mocambo. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Guinia ~25 cm standoff	3899MH00190001401499C00	1499	autofocus sub-frame for target Guinia - standoff near 25 cm
		3899MH00190001401500C00	1500	target Guinia - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Guinia stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3899MH00299001401501C00	1501	autofocus sub-frame for target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3899MH00299001401502C00	1502	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3899MH00299001401503C00	1503	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401504C00	1504	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401505C00	1505	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401506C00	1506	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401507C00	1507	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401508C00	1508	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401509C00	1509	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401510C00	1510	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Guinia stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3899MH00299001401511C00	1511	autofocus sub-frame for target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3899MH00299001401512C00	1512	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3899MH00299001401513C00	1513	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401514C00	1514	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401515C00	1515	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401516C00	1516	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401517C00	1517	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401518C00	1518	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401519C00	1519	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00299001401520C00	1520	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00335	Guinia ~2 cm standoff	3899MH00335001401521C00	1521	autofocus sub-frame for target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm
		3899MH00335001401522C00	1522	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm
		3899MH00335001401523C00	1523	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401524C00	1524	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401525C00	1525	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401526C00	1526	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401527C00	1527	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401528C00	1528	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401529C00	1529	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00335001401530C00	1530	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Mocambo ~24 cm standoff	3899MH00190001401531C00	1531	autofocus sub-frame for target Mocambo - standoff near 24 cm
		3899MH00190001401532C00	1532	target Mocambo - standoff near 24 cm
mN00398	Mocambo stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3899MH00398001401533C00	1533	autofocus sub-frame for target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3899MH00398001401534C00	1534	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3899MH00398001401535C00	1535	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401536C00	1536	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401537C00	1537	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401538C00	1538	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401539C00	1539	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401540C00	1540	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401541C00	1541	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401542C00	1542	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00398	Mocambo stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3899MH00398001401543C00	1543	autofocus sub-frame for target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3899MH00398001401544C00	1544	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3899MH00398001401545C00	1545	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401546C00	1546	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401547C00	1547	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401548C00	1548	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401549C00	1549	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401550C00	1550	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401551C00	1551	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3899MH00398001401552C00	1552	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3899MH002270001401553R00	1553	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1545-1552 - best focus image product
		3899MH002270001401554R00	1554	target Mocambo - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1545-1552 - range map product
		3899MH002270001401555R00	1555	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1535-1542 - best focus image product
		3899MH002270001401556R00	1556	target Mocambo - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1535-1542 - range map product
		3899MH002270001401557R00	1557	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1523-1530 - best focus image product
		3899MH002270001401558R00	1558	target Guinia - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1523-1530 - range map product
		3899MH002270001401559R00	1559	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1513-1520 - best focus image product
		3899MH002270001401560R00	1560	target Guinia - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1513-1520 - range map product
		3899MH002270001401561R00	1561	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1503-1510 - best focus image product
		3899MH002270001401562R00	1562	target Guinia - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3899 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1503-1510 - range map product

updated: 07_August_2023

Sol 3900 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27 Jul 23
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Porta_Walter and the target Purace.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Porta_Walter after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3900MH001900014015630CD	1563	autofocus sub-frame for target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3900MH001900014015640CD	1564	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Porta_Walter after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3900MH001680014015650CD	1565	autofocus sub-frame for target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015660CD	1566	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015670CD	1567	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015680CD	1568	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015690CD	1569	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015700CD	1570	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015710CD	1571	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015720CD	1572	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015730CD	1573	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015740CD	1574	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Porta_Walter after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3900MH001680014015750CD	1575	autofocus sub-frame for target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015760CD	1576	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015770CD	1577	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015780CD	1578	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015790CD	1579	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015800CD	1580	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015810CD	1581	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015820CD	1582	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015830CD	1583	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014015840CD	1584	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Porta_Walter after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3900MH007430014015850CD	1585	autofocus sub-frame for target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3900MH007430014015860CD	1586	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3900MH007430014015870CD	1587	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015880CD	1588	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015890CD	1589	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015900CD	1590	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015910CD	1591	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015920CD	1592	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015930CD	1593	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH007430014015940CD	1594	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Purace ~24 cm standoff	3900MH001900014015950CD	1595	autofocus sub-frame for target Purace - standoff near 24 cm
		3900MH001900014015960CD	1596	target Purace - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Purace stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3900MH001680014015970CD	1597	autofocus sub-frame for target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015980CD	1598	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014015990CD	1599	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016000CD	1600	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016010CD	1601	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016020CD	1602	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016030CD	1603	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016040CD	1604	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016050CD	1605	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016060CD	1606	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Purace stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3900MH001680014016070CD	1607	autofocus sub-frame for target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014016080CD	1608	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3900MH001680014016090CD	1609	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016100CD	1610	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016110CD	1611	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016120CD	1612	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016130CD	1613	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016140CD	1614	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016150CD	1615	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3900MH001680014016160CD	1616	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 28_July_2023

Sol 3901 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	28 Jul 23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities:	Focus stack images from Sol 3900 were merged.
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3901MH0002270001401617900	1617	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1609-1616 - best focus image product
		3901MH0002270001401618500	1618	target Purace - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1609-1616 - range map product
		3901MH0002270001401619900	1619	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1599-1606 - best focus image product
		3901MH0002270001401620500	1620	target Purace - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1599-1606 - range map product
		3901MH0002270001401621900	1621	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1587-1594 - best focus image product
		3901MH0002270001401622500	1622	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1587-1594 - range map product
		3901MH0002270001401623900	1623	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1577-1584 - best focus image product
		3901MH0002270001401624500	1624	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1577-1584 - range map product
		3901MH0002270001401625900	1625	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1567-1574 - best focus image product
		3901MH0002270001401626500	1626	target Porta_Walter - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3900 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1567-1574 - range map product

updated: 02_August_2023

Sol 3902 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jul 23
camera position	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	33

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Jamari.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Jamari after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3902MH001900014016270CD	1627	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3902MH001900014016280CD	1628	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002168	Jamari after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3902MH001680014016300CD	1629	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3902MH001680014016300CD	1630	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3902MH001680014016310CD	1631	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016320CD	1632	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016330CD	1633	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016340CD	1634	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016350CD	1635	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016360CD	1636	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016370CD	1637	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016380CD	1638	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Jamari after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3902MH001680014016390CD	1639	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3902MH001680014016400CD	1640	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3902MH001680014016410CD	1641	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016420CD	1642	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016430CD	1643	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016440CD	1644	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016450CD	1645	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016460CD	1646	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016470CD	1647	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH001680014016480CD	1648	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Jamari after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3902MH007430014016490CD	1649	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3902MH007430014016500CD	1650	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3902MH007430014016510CD	1651	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016520CD	1652	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016530CD	1653	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016540CD	1654	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016550CD	1655	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016560CD	1656	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016570CD	1657	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3902MH007430014016580CD	1658	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

Acknowledgements

The MAHLI investigation was developed and operated under subcontracts to Malin Space Science Systems in collaboration with JPL-Caltech (Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology) under the direction of NASA. JPL-Caltech manages the MSL mission for NASA. MAHLI instrument operations and science are supported by a team of personnel at Malin Space Science Systems, the Planetary Science Institute, JPL-Caltech, and across the USA and the world; they are all thanked for their monumental efforts to assist in the success of the investigation.

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